

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D 9.4 Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities

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SUMMARY	<p>This document is the deliverable D9.4 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 9 (Exploitation and Dissemination of the results, Communication).</p> <p>This is a summary of the actions implemented in dissemination and communication since the beginning of the project and a report on the concrete actions related to the protection and exploitation of the project results (including dissemination and communication activities) undertaken during the project duration toward the objectives (PEDR) and evaluation of their impact.</p>
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
Acronym	POLYPHEM
Call identifier	H2020 LCE-07-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement N°	764048
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Beneficiaries	CNRS, CEA, CIEMAT, Arraela S.L., Fraunhofer ISE, Kaefer Isoliertechnik, Orcan Energy, Euronovia, Aalborg CSP

The POLYPHEM project was a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It was implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim was to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consisted in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver was integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage used a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project was to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress was a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications were considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh was designed, built, and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project was to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ANEST	Associazione Nazionale Energia Solare Termodinamica
ARRA	Arraela
AUSTCAELA	Australian Solar Thermal Energy Association
BPD	Business Plan Development
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCGT	Combined Cycle Gas Turbine
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
DCSP	Deutscher Industrieverband Concentrated Solar Power
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ESS	Exploitation Strategy Seminar
ESTELA	European Solar Thermal Electricity Association
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	Innovation Advisory Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISB	International Standardization Bodies
KAE	Kaefer SE
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
M	Month
MS	Milestone
MW	Mégawatts
NCP	National contact points
OA	Open Access
ORC	Orcan Energy GmbH or Organic Rankine Cycle
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results
PROTERMOSOLAR	Asociacion Espanola para la Promocion de la Industria Termosolar
PU	Public
SER	Syndicat des Energies Renouvelables
SASTELA	Southern Africa Solar Thermal and Electricity Association
STELAWORLD	World Solar Thermal Electricity Association
WP	Work Package

INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 9.4 is the Final report on the POLYPHEM project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on

innovation. It also includes a detailed report of all dissemination and communication activities that were performed during the project from Month 1 until Month 53.

This deliverable falls within Work Package 9 on communication, dissemination and exploitation of the results, whose objectives are to:

- **Identify** the potential different routes for innovation and exploitation of the project results, as well as the protection of intellectual property rights in order to maximize the post-project's impact on the participating organizations, the industry as well as on the community at-large;
- **Disseminate** the information about the POLYPHEM project to a wide range of relevant stakeholders and to the public at large through various dissemination activities in order to engage the community behind the project;
- **Ensure** maximum visibility of the project through tailored communication activities in order to raise awareness about the potential of CSP and POLYPHEM.

Euronovia is the leading beneficiary in charge of writing this deliverable and manages the dissemination, communication, and exploitation actions.

All partners have responsibilities in their role as disseminator of the project results. According to the Grant Agreement and unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

1. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

1.1 PLAN FOR EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION OF THE PROJECT RESULTS

Dissemination and communication should be understood as follows:

- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. Disclosure may sound passive, like a shop opening up, but it is an activity, like a shopkeeper attracting customers. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organized at the beginning of each project, usually in a dissemination plan.
- **Communication** means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

The specific objectives for dissemination and communication are to:

- Ensure high visibility of the project among key stakeholders through the management and use of appropriate communication channels;
- Design specific actions aimed at the scientific community and general public (including business and political stakeholders);
- Engage and ensure collaboration with industry and end-users;
- Ensure that all project partners can identify and understand the information needs of specific target audiences;
- Design and conduct the dissemination and engagement strategy.

The **Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results (PEDR)** (see Deliverable D9.2) explains how the dissemination and communication strategy was built and performed. It presents the methodology adopted for different aspects of the strategy:

- Definition of the **target groups** (policy makers, end-users, industries, R&D stakeholders, all relevant to thermal storage, CSP, renewable energies, etc.)
- Definition of the **message to be delivered** (enhancing the role of renewable energies and CSP, demonstrating the positive impact of POLYPHEM solutions, showing the development of the project, etc.)
- Selection of the **communication channels** (website, emails, press releases, publications, journal articles, conferences, workshops, etc.)
- Planning of the **implementation** (timing, costs and human resources needed, etc.)
- Development of **Key Performance Indicators** (KPIs) to assess the success of the implementation (number of publications, number of emails received from stakeholders, number of visits on the website, feedback received from audiences at conferences, surveys, etc.)

The following sub-sections provides an overview of the content of the PEDR.

1.2 TARGET GROUPS

POLYPHEM tried to address the widest audience as possible, with specific messages and channel of communications for each type of audience. Mapping closely the audience was essential in choosing the most efficient ways to disseminate the project results. Within the audience, we defined several groups that have an interest or are going to be affected by the project. These groups are classified in three categories, taking into account their level of interest and their level of power.

The targeted audience has been defined since the beginning of the project in relation to the results and deliverables of the project. The main target groups for the dissemination activities are:

- Universities and Research Institutes,
- The industry networks,
- Policy makers and Research funding agencies,
- Mass media,
- The general public.

For each of these types of audience presented, we have identified direct contacts to disseminate the information on the project. The list presented below is non-exhaustive and has been provided as examples. Constant research was done to regularly update the contact database used to disseminate the information.

Regarding the research organisations, a database has been gathered compiling data from the consortium, other events, or the market test, enabling the creation of a quality network to be used for dissemination, communication, and further exploitation.

The first two audiences (Universities and Research Institutes, and industry networks) are the main group within the dissemination target audience. A major part of the dissemination actions targeted to these two groups. This is where we were expecting the maximum impact in terms of potential collaborations and future exploitation. This is composed of:

- The **research and academic community** active in the field of concentrated solar power, solar tower technology, micro-gas-turbines, thermal storage, small-scale solar heat, and power cogeneration.
- **Potential end-users industry**, and in particular their executive officers, related technology clusters.

The third audience related to policy-makers and funding agencies is composed of actors affected by the success of the project, although not identified as primary target group.

- Policy makers and funding agencies in country or regions with a strong solar or water desalination industry
- Investors and business actors

Finally, the last two audiences consist of the general public and other actors that can find interest in the project:

- Mass media
- Partners' local stakeholders

- General public

This final group was more targeted by the general communication actions since the project scientific results might be too narrowed for them and a more general and vulgarized message on the project should be sent to them, like the creation of the general brochure or videos.

The targeted audience was constantly updated throughout the lifetime of the project in relation to the results and deliverables. In particular, starting from M7 and until the end of the project and after, POLYPHEM was in charge of looking for potential end-users and thus contributed to the extension of the list, especially with the market study who had provided a relevant list of industrial stakeholders interested in the project.

As explained, the targeted audience has been defined since the beginning of the project in relation to the results and deliverables of the project.

The main target groups for the communication and dissemination activities are presented below:

Academic and research community	This group targets all research communities interested in the POLYPHEM project's developments, results and innovation which can be beneficiary for their own research activities. Scientific contributions of POLYPHEM are particularly interesting for researchers working in the field of development of CSP, thermal storage, small-scale electricity production, ...
Industrial sector, Professional Associations	<p>A major objective of POLYPHEM was to address and trigger the active involvement of industrial and user communities. POLYPHEM was of relevance for organizations in various industry activities and that implied the necessity to approach them individually in the dissemination actions.</p> <p>A general market study on the project technology innovation has been organized digitally to gain responses from the different industrial segments at a worldwide level. This has brought important information for further exploitation of the project results and enabled a better focus of the project on the stakeholders needs.</p> <p>An innovation advisory board (IAB) targeted directly at the industry sector has also been created. They provided valuable feedback on the project, introducing challenging requirements to be considered and had a major impact on the project's sustainable development.</p> <p>Dedicated seminars were organized to improve the POLYPHEM exploitation strategy of its results with professional and external experts.</p>
International Standardization Bodies (ISB)	ISB should be aware of POLYPHEM scope and objectives. In a future potential advanced stage of the project, ISB could be involved and provide consultative advice on pre-standardization procedures which may be carried out when the technology reaches a suitable readiness level.
Government bodies and policy makers	This was a wide group encompassing innovation driven local and regional authorities, representatives and associations, Ministries, parliaments, and Public Administrations at national and international level. There are several significant goals that can be promoted for them and especially the promotion of the use of renewable energies and the possibilities to improve the environmental performance at low risk, with a better performance and by reducing the LCOE. Thus, the POLYPHEM technology will contribute towards expected EC sustainable emission targets.
EU technology Clusters	This group refers to activities addressing external task forces that can be relevant to POLYPHEM and which will offer a quite big and reusable knowledge base for disseminating on the project. Relevant European technology clusters have been identified, such as the

	DERBI Cluster and the Atlansun Cluster on renewable and solar energies in France, the SOLARTYS cluster in Spain on Solar Energy & Energy Efficiency, etc.
EU projects working in similar domain	The participation of project partners in other relevant projects offered the opportunity to establish quick links among parties through common participants (see 1.3.1.2)
The general public	This group encompasses a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project especially regarding the raise of awareness of the importance of solar energy as a credible alternative for the future.

Table 1 - POLYPHEM Main target groups for the dissemination activities

1.3 METHODS TO BUILD THE AUDIENCE CONTACT DATABASE

- Automatic plug-in on the website to give the possibilities to interested people to register for the newsletters;
- Participation to conferences and establishment of contacts with new stakeholders via exhibition conferences, B2B meetings, other networking events;
- Data gathering from market studies;
- General internet search;
- Internal partners network;
- Existing database from previous projects.

For each of these organizations presented below, we have identified direct contacts to disseminate the information on the project. The list presented below is non-exhaustive and has been provided as examples. Constant research was done to regularly update the contact database used to disseminate the information.

1.3.1 Research community

1.3.1.1 Research centers

The contact database that we have built to disseminate the information on the project encompasses most of the EU research centers and outside EU dealing with CSP. This has been done thanks to previous collaborations in different EU projects, via the project network, through actual participations to events or thanks to the market test.

The research centers included in the list are organizations like (non-exhaustive):

- CIEMAT-PSA (Spain)
- CNRS-PROMES (France)
- CEA (France)
- Fraunhofer (Germany)
- DLR (Germany)
- ENEA (Italy)
- CENER (Spain)
- Cranfield University (UK)
- IK4 Tekniker (Spain)
- Leitat Institute (Spain)
- Evora University (Portugal)
- Cyprus Institute (Cyprus)
- Sandia Lab (US)
- CSIRO (Australia)
- NREL (US)
- CNR (Italy)
- Stellenbosch (South Africa)
- Iresen (Morocco)
- Masdar (UAE)
- Kier (Korea)

1.3.1.2 Other EU funded projects

Other R&D European projects funded by Horizon 2020 and that are directly linked to CSP technologies (dissemination via their Coordinators could be also useful) are considered as very important for dissemination in the scientific community. Actions have been implemented in collaboration with them. This

list is non-exhaustive and year after year, after each EU call, the consortium has tried to map the newcomers in the CSP technologies.

Activities of collaboration are already going on and were realised with these projects through:

- the creation and promotion of a joint CSP newsletter,
- the organisation of joint workshops and joint booths at CSP conferences,
- the management of LinkedIn account,
- the management of a twitter account.

A telephone conference was happening every 3 months between the dissemination WP leaders of each of these projects in order to map the potential joint actions to plan.

Project	Title	Objective	Website
ORC-PLUS	Organic Rankine Cycle - Prototype Link to Unit Storage	Increasing energy storage to optimise power generation from a concentrated solar power plant	http://www.orc-plus.eu/
PreFlexMS	Predictable Flexible Molten Salts Solar Power Plant	Demonstrating a novel steam generator technology and a weather forecast/dispatch optimisation software in a concentrating solar power plant	http://preflexms.eu/
CAPTure	Competitive Solar Power Towers – CAPTure	Demonstrating a new type of concentrating solar power plant that combines several towers and heliostat fields	http://capture-solar-energy.eu/
SOLPART	High Temperature Solar-Heated Reactors for Industrial Production of Reactive Particulates	Developing at pilot scale a process suitable for particle treatment in energy intensive industries (e.g. cement or lime industries), by using high-temperature solar heat to provide thermal energy required for CaCO ₃ calcination	http://www.solpart-project.eu/
SUN-to-LIQUID	SUNlight-to-LIQUID: Integrated solar-thermochemical synthesis of liquid hydrocarbon fuels	Advancing solar fuels well beyond the state of the art and to guide the further scale-up towards a reliable basis for competitive industrial exploitation	http://www.sun-to-liquid.eu/
MinWaterCSP	MinWaterCSP - Minimized water consumption in CSP plants	Developing solutions to drastically reduce water consumption in the operation of concentrating solar power plants	http://www.minwatercsp.eu/
WASCOP	Water Saving for Solar Concentrated Power	Minimising water consumption in concentrating solar power plant operation	http://wascop.eu/
RAISELIFE	Raising the Lifetime of Functional Materials for Concentrated Solar Power Technology	Extending the in-service lifetime of five key materials for concentrated solar power technologies	https://www.raiselife.eu/
NEXT-CSP	High Temperature concentrated solar thermal power plan with particle receiver and direct thermal storage	Developing a new system for heat transfer fluids and high-temperature receivers to obtain high efficiency power cycles (>50 %) in order to increase the efficiency of a concentrated solar power plant by 20%	http://www.next-csp.eu/
PEGASUS	Renewable Power Generation by Solar Particle Receiver Driven Sulphur Storage Cycle	Investigating a novel power cycle for renewable electricity production by applying a solar particle receiver with a sulphur storage system for base load operation	https://www.pegasus-project.eu/

MOSAIC	MODular high concentration SolAR Configuration	Developing a new type of concentrated solar power plant based on a modular design using a novel high-concentration mirror concept	http://mosaic-h2020.eu/
INSHIP	Integrating National Research Agendas on Solar Heat for Industrial Processes	Engaging major European research institutes with recognized activities on SHIP, into an integrated structure	http://inship.eu/
IN-POWER	Advanced Materials technologies to QUADRUPLE the Concentrated Solar Thermal current POWER GENERATION	Develop High efficiency solar harvesting CSP architectures based on holistic materials and innovative manufacturing process	http://in-power-project.eu/
MUSTEC	Market uptake of Solar Thermal Electricity through Cooperation	Assess the existing barriers and opportunities for concentrated solar power that could play a key role in the future European electricity system by supplying electricity from Southern to Northern European countries	http://www.mustec.eu/
SFERA-III	Solar Facilities for the European Research Area	The overall objective of this project is to carry on with the work done during the past 8 years in the SFERA 1 and SFERA 2 projects and reinforce the sustainability of the activities of the European advanced Concentrating Solar Power research infrastructures.	https://sfera3.sollab.eu/
SOCRATCES	Solar Calcium-looping integRation for Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage	Demonstrating the feasibility to integrating Calcium-looping process (CaL) and concentrated solar power (CSP) plants for thermochemical energy storage and power generation	https://socratces.eu/
SHIP2FAIR	Solar Heat for Industrial Process towards Food and Agro Industries Commitment in Renewables	Demonstrating solar heat integration in four open-to-public industrial sites covering sugar, wine, spirits and meat sectors	http://ship2fair-h2020.eu/
SOLWATT	Solving Water Issues for CSP Plants	Demonstration at two sites that water consumption can be reduced with innovations in the solar field cleaning techniques, power-block cooling, water recycling system, and with optimised plant operation strategy	https://solwatt.eu/
HYCOOL	Industrial Cooling through Hybrid system based on Solar Heat	Increasing the current use of solar heat in industrial processes by developing a combined system based on new Fresnel concentrated solar collectors and hybrid heat pumps	http://hycool-project.eu/project/

Table 2 - Related EU funded projects

1.3.2 Industry sector

1.3.2.1 Companies in the field of CSP

These companies have been mapped as some key stakeholders in the CSP field since they are some of the biggest MW installer of CSP plants and are more experienced to step in an innovative project. Contacts from these companies have been added into the database.

Company	Website	Country
Sener	http://www.poweroilandgas.sener/solar	Spain
GE	https://www.ge.com/renewableenergy/innovative-solutions/solar-energy/concentrated-solar-power	United States
Abengoa	http://www.abengoa.com/web/en/negocio/energia/electricidad_solar/termosolar/index.htm	Spain
ACS Cobra	http://www.grupocobra.com/areas-de-negocio/proyectos-integrados/plantas-de-generacion-electrica/renovables/solar/	
Acciona	https://www.acciona.com/news/acciona-sells-its-solar-thermal-assets-spain-contourglobal/	
TSK	http://www.flagsol.com/flagsol/cms/	
Lanzhou Dacheng	http://www.lzdc solar.com/EN/About%20Dacheng/about/	China
NWEPDI	http://www.nwepdi.com/EnNwepdi/SitePages/ywgk/NewEnergyDesign/NewEnergy.aspx?nid=3	
Beijing Shouhang IHW Resources Saving Technology	http://en.sh-ihw.com/product_class/pmclid=43.html	

Table 3 - Companies in the field of CSP

Other companies in the CSP-related field have been identified:

Linear fresnel:

Feranova
Novatec Solar
Suncnim
Industrial Solar
ExirSolar

Dish technology (Stirling):

HelioFocus
ZED Solar
Azelio AB

Operation and maintenance:

Smit Group

Auxiliary and anti-freezing boiler:

Sugimat SL

Steam turbine erection:

Smit Group

Pre-operational cleaning:

Smit Ingeniería
Solarca

Parabolic trough

Ervis Technology
GlassPoint Solar
Helioclim
Parvolen
Rackam

Schott Mirrors and Receiver Tubes

Royal Tech CSP
SkyFuel

Sopogy Micro CSP

Ultra Lite Solar

Solar tower technology:

ABROS green GmbH
Aora Solar, formerly E.D.I.G. Solar Distributed Solar Thermal
BrightSource Energy / Luz II
CMI Solar
Greenway CSP
Torresol Energy

1.3.2.2 The industry networks

Industrial associations related to CSP in general

- EU associations like ESTELA¹, Deutsche CSP²(Germany), Protermosolar³(Spain), Anest (Italy), SER (France)
- ESTELA international network: AUSTELA⁴(Australia), Sastela⁵(South-Africa), STELAWORLD⁶(World)
- China National Solar Thermal Energy Alliance – China
- Solar Energy Corporation of India (SECI) - India
- Solar Energy Industries Association (SEIA) – USA
- Emirates Solar Industry Association (ESIA) – UAE
- Saudi Arabia Solar Industry Association (SASIA) – Saudi Arabia

Other EU associations related to solar and renewables in general

- EASE - The European Association for Storage of Energy – Europe
- EERA – European Energy Research Alliance – Europe
- ESTIF - European Solar Thermal Industry Federation – Europe
- EDS - European Desalination Society – Europe
- REA - Renewable Energy Association – UK
- EUREC - The Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centers

EU National Contact Points (NCP)

- The Energy team: <http://www.c-energyplus.eu/>
- The Environment team: <http://www.env-ncp-together.eu/>
- The NMP (Nanotechnologies Materials and Production) team: <http://www.nmpteam.com/index.html>
- The Research Infrastructure team: <http://www.euroris-net.eu/>

The NCPs are an excellent network to promote the project since they directly disseminate the information to their whole network ranging from public institutes to industries.

EU SME support organisations

- EBN - European Business & Innovation Centre Network
- EuroChambers - The Association of European Chambers of Commerce and Industry
- EEN – Enterprise Europe Network – To find a local partner for the EEN: <http://een.ec.europa.eu/about/branches>

The SME support organisations are also of importance since this enables to promote better the potential exploitation activities to a wide range of SMEs.

Worldwide stakeholders

- The online Platform for CSP – Brazil
- The International Solar Energy Society (ISES) – International
- The International Energy Agency (IEA) – International
- The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) – International
- SolarPACES -Technology Cooperation Programme of IEA– International

The list is not exhaustive but is just an example of the large database and communication power that the project has, seeing his wide network and experience with international networks.

¹ <http://estelasolar.org>

² <https://deutsche-csp.de/>

³ <https://www.protermosolar.com/>

⁴ <http://helioscsp.com/tag/australian-solar-thermal-energy-association/>

⁵ <http://sastela.org/>

⁶ <http://www.stelaworld.org/>

1.3.3 Funding associations

These agencies are part of the Solar Era net network and can be contacted when needed to reach policy and funding stakeholders to communicate on the events and other achievements. This takes all its importance for the post-project dissemination and mid-term vision for the upscale of the technology.

Country / Region	Funding Organisation or Contact Point	Contact(s) and Domain(s)
Austria	Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG)	Anita Hipfinger: anita.hipfinger@ffg.at, +43 5 7755 5025
Belgium-Flanders	Vlaams Agentschap Innoveren en Ondernemen	Geert Carchon: geert.carchon@vlaio.be, +32 2 432 42 94 Bart De Caesemaeker: bart.decaesemaeker@vlaio.be, +32 2 432 42 49
Belgium-Wallonia	Service Public de Wallonie (SPW)	DGO4-Department of sustainable energy and buildings Laurence Polain: laurence.polain@spw-wallonie.be, +32 81 486342
Cyprus	Research Promotion Foundation (RPF)	Pavlos Leptos: pleptos@research.org.cy, +357 22205026
France	Agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie (ADEME)	Tristan Carrere, Ingénieur Photovoltaïque, tristan.carrere@ademe.fr, +33 (0)1 47 65 23 51
France	Agence Nationale de la recherche (ANR)	Aurélien Gaufrès: Aurelien.gaufres@agencerecherche.fr, +33 1 73 54 82 29 Pascal Bain: Pascal.Bain@agencerecherche.fr, +33 1 78 09 80 43
Germany	Projekträger Jülich (PtJ)	Geschäftsbereich Energiesystem: Erneuerbare Energien/Kraftwerkstechnik, Fachbereich Photovoltaik (ESE 1) Renate Horbelt: r.horbelt@fz-juelich.de, +49 2461 61 9874 Kambulakwao Chakanga: k.chakanga@fz-juelich.de, +49 2461 61 9871
Germany-NRW	Projekträger ETN	Fachbereich Energie Dr. Melanie Schulte: me.schulte@fz-juelich.de, +49 2461 690 504 Dr. Joachim Kutscher: jo.kutsche@fz-juelich.de, +49 2461 690 604
Greece	General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT)	Paraskevi Afentaki International S&T Cooperation Directorate Bilateral and Multilateral Cooperation Section +302107458112
Israel	Ministry of Energy	Gideon Friedmann, Head of R&D Division - Office of the Chief Scientist, +972-2-5316020 (Office), +972-2-5316017 (Fax), +972-58-5337565 (Mobile), gideonf@energy.gov.il
Italy	Ministry for Education, University and Research (MIUR)	Ing. Aldo Covello tel. +39 06 9772 6465 e-mail: aldo.covello@miur.it Dott. Andrea Previti - tel: (+39) 06 5849 7146 e-mail: andrea.previti@est.miur.it
Netherlands	RVO	Otto Bernsen, otto.bernsen@rvo.nl Wijnand van Hooff, wijnand@tki-urbanenergy.nl
Spain-CDTI	Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (CDTI)	Gabriel Barthelemy: gabriel.barthelemy@cdti.es, +34 91 581 0707

Table 4 National / Regional Funding Organisation Contact Points in solar energies⁷

⁷ http://www.solar-era.net/index.php/download_file/view/402/140/

1.4 POLYPHEM MESSAGE

When defining the messages to be delivered, different questions⁸ can be asked in order to properly set the relevant messages depending on the audience:

- Is it news?
- Why do we need to know?
- What will change? What solutions are you offering?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- Have you tried to stir your audience's imagination and emotions?
- How does your work relate to everyday life? Does it link to any broader societal issue?
- Rather than focusing only on the provision of factual information, is your project research positioned within a broader socio-economic and policy context, so that it will be easier to explain the results and their relevance to policymakers and citizens?
- Are you connecting to what your audience wants to know? See through your audience's eyes?
- What do they already know about the topic?
- What do they think about it?
- Do they need information and/or persuasion?
- Have you tested your message?
- Are you connecting to your own communication objectives?

There are many ways to communicate on the project activities and results. Here are some messages that had been promoted through the dissemination activities:

- Enhance the role of Renewable Energy to ensure people are aware of their benefits for the environment, society, and life of the citizens;
- Advertise the POLYPHEM project itself (general scope, coverage, goals, and milestones and plans to reach them);
- Enhance the role played by POLYPHEM in the European solar industry by showcasing the project potential;
- Demonstrate the positive impact of POLYPHEM's solutions in the wide spectrum of solar technologies by promoting the POLYPHEM advantages (water saving, 100% solar electricity, cost effectiveness, CO2 saving, ...);
- Promote the study and construction of the prototype to show the European capacities in developing industrial solutions;
- Advertise POLYPHEM results (reached objectives and achievements), techniques and methodologies (taking due care of IPR issues), technologies (taking due care of IPR issues), sustainability assessment results, and innovation aspects (in an "open innovation" perspective);
- Recall the importance of involving key users and public authorities at local, regional, and national levels in the project in order to guarantee the back-up of the project by key stakeholders.
- Show how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness, and solving societal challenges;
- Make better use of the results, by making sure they are taken-up by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up, and also by decision-makers to influence policy-making.

1.5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

POLYPHEM partners asked themselves the following questions when planning and executing the dissemination and communication channels:

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

- Do they reach the audience?
- Are you working at the right level (local, regional, national)?
- Are you using dissemination partners and multipliers? Dissemination partners can help amplify and multiply a message. Rather than aiming to build an audience from scratch, the project should indicate which partners to use and how.
- Do they go beyond the obvious?
- If input or contributions are needed, are there mechanisms in place to make communication interactive so as to obtain responses?
- Are you taking into account the different ways to communicate?

Here below is a figure presenting how the targeted audience was reached through the project dissemination and communication activities.

Figure 1 - POLYPHEM Targeted Audiences

The following table gives an overview of the dissemination and communication actions that were carried out in POLYPHEM as planned in the DoA and presented in the PEDR.

For most of the actions some KPIs have been originally fixed. Some actions have been added to this plan (like the final brochure or media press kit or webinars, due to the COVID situation), some others have been modified depending on the relevance of the action.

POLYPHEM – EU-H2020 Grant Agreement N°764048

Communication/Dissemination activity	Timing	Main objective	Main Targeted audience	Main KPI	Quantification of KPI
Peer-reviewed scientific publications (Open Access) in journals	All along the project and after its completion	Inform and promote about the scientific results of the project Transfer of knowledge	Scientific Community	Number of publications	10 publications in journals
Participation in conferences (presentation of posters or scientific papers)	All along the project and after its completion	Promote the scientific results to interested groups and interact with other related technologies	Scientific Community Industry Policy-makers Other: RI users	Number of conferences Number of posters or oral presentation Number of participants to the conference	10 conferences attended 10 posters Min 200 participants
Three participations to trade/scientific fairs	Year 2, 3 and 4	Promote the results and engage with the industry for the enhancement of the exploitation of the scientific results	Industry Policy makers related to solar/renewables technology Other: RI users	Number of participants to the exhibition fairs Number of visitors of the stand	Minimum 200 participants 20 visitors per event
One technical workshop to present the project technology and work plan Hosting partner: to be defined at M6	M12	Promote the technology Commit the community into more personal interactions with the project Present the technology and receive feedback	Scientific Community Industry	Number of attendees to the workshop	20 attendees per event
One training course Hosting partner: to be defined M6	M24	Transfer of knowledge to students through a manual Attract Master students, PhD students and post-docs to engage into renewable energies	Scientific Community (Education, Universities where courses related to the field are delivered)	Number of attendees to the training	20 attendees
One open infoday Hosting partner: to be defined at M6	M36	Provide better scientific and technological understanding to non-scientific stakeholders Make science more accessible to non-specialists	General public	Number of attendees to the Open Info Day	Min 40 participants
One business workshop presenting the economic and environmental assessment Hosting partner: To be defined at M6	M48	Provide better scientific and technological understanding to non-scientific stakeholders -Present the LCA and risk issues of the technology -Raise funds for the further development of the technology	Policy-makers, industries, investors, environmental organizations, all related to Renewable Energy Systems. EU and worldwide Industrial Associations (ESTELA,...)	Number of attendees to the business workshop	20 attendees
Technical reports in the form of the deliverables – all public deliverables	All along the project	Publish online and open access to the scientific results	General public (interested groups)	Number of reports uploaded from the website	All deliverables
POLYPHEM website	M3	Raise awareness, inform, engage, promote the project & the results.	General public	Number of visitors	50 visitors / month
Social web-based media (especially LinkedIn and Twitter) and presence on the web (especially Wikipedia)	All along the project	To make science more accessible to a wider public	General public (especially targeted for a younger public who engages more with social media)	Number of news published Number of followers	15 news per year 200 followers at the end of the project
2 brochures, 8 joint newsletters (together with other CSP projects), 2 press releases, 1 video, 2 articles in magazines	All along the project	Inform about the project Promote the project innovative concept	Scientific Community Industry Policy makers Media General public	Number of subscribers to the newsletter Number of recipients of the brochures Number of views of the videos	50 500 200
School visits by the PhD students	Year 2 and 3	Popularize science by making it attractive Create interest in younger generation to follow science careers	Young pupils as well as teachers	Number of school visits	1 per PhD student
Interviews of the partners disseminated on the web	Fourth year of the project	Inform about the project Promote the project innovative concept	General public	Views of video	200 views average
Media press kit to be disseminated	At the end of the project	Inform the general public	Media	Number of citations of the project on internet	20
Webinars	From year 3 until the end	Reach a wider community and enable for better dissemination of project results in spite of restrictions for participation to physical events and incapacity to organize workshop	Scientific Community Industry	Number of webinars Attendance to the webinar	Min. 2 Min. 40

Table 5 - POLYPHEM Dissemination and Communication activities

1.6 PLANNING OF THE ACTIVITIES

The planning and execution of the activities required a good scheduling closely aligned with key project deliverables. The Gantt Chart and activities were planned according to 3 different phases:

- 1) Initial awareness phase (month 0-6):** this phase especially included establishment of the project website, analysis of relevant information resources in terms of identification of dissemination opportunities and creation of basic dissemination tools including graphical identity of the project (i.e. project logo, templates for project documents and for project presentations). A market study was organized to have a first attempt at validating the project objectives towards a worldwide database of interested stakeholders.
- 2) Targeted dissemination phase (month 6-36):** during this phase, the consortium enriched the website, published a project brochure, issued the newsletters, and attended selected events. Preliminary project results were presented to the target audiences.
- 3) Presentation of results (month 36-53):** this represents the period closely before the end of the project when POLYPHEM reaches its most significant outputs. This phase was focused on informing the target audience for the exploitation.

Although a certain amount of dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime, the most significant dissemination activities took place when research results became available and actual experimentation takes place in the last 2 years of the project.

Therefore, it is important to notice that the first two years were not the most active, but the final year and months were strong.

The GANTT chart below gives an indication of the scheduling of the dissemination and communication activities. This schedule has changed as the project goes along, to ensure that sufficient results or news were disseminated at each step. This third version is already an update of the first and second ones that were submitted in the PEDR and includes the actions of what has been achieved so far.

POLYPHEM – EU-H2020 Grant Agreement N°764048

	Year 1			Year 2				Year 3				Year 4				Year 5			After project				
	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
COMMUNICATION ON PROJECT ACTIVITIES																							
Visual identity (logo and templates)	■																						
Public website (M3) and regular updates		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Social media (LinkedIn and Twitter)		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
E-newsletters (1 every 6 months)			■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■		■
Posters																		■					
Infographic timeline																		■					
Brochures (M6 - M40)		■										■			■								
Videos												■						■	■				
Media press kit																		■	■				
Press release and articles in magazines																		■	■				
Online presence in generic media		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
DISSEMINATION OF PROJECT RESULTS																							
Peer-reviewed publications								■					■			■			■				
Open access repository created								■	■	■													
Participation in conferences (orals / posters)			■				■				■			■						■			
Public technical deliverables		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
EVENTS																							
Exhibition to trade fairs / science conference			■				■				■			■									
Workshops and final infoday							Cancelled due to C-19				Cancelled due to C-19							■					
Webinars																		■	■				
Popularization events and generic public events	■	■	■		■		■											■	■				
JOINT ACTIONS WITH H2020 CSP PROJECTS																							

Table 6 - POLYPHEM Gantt Chart activities

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIONS IMPLEMENTED

2.1 VISUAL IDENTITY CREATED

The visual identity of POLYPHEM included a **logo** (see below), and style in **different formats** (in line with the H2020 visual guidelines), as well as the website, brochures, and other dissemination materials that were created all along the project depending on the dissemination and communication needs.

Once the visual identity was ready, a standard **PowerPoint** template was used for official presentations and a **Word template** was created (mainly for deliverables). These templates were sent to partners for EU and local project communication.

2.1.1 Logo

The pictograph of the **logo** is a stylistic representation of a solar tower, including the colors of the sky and the sun. The logo was used for all communication materials, either in color or in black, depending on the background color. There is also a baseline, which, depending on the size of the logo to be printed, can be optional or not.

2.1.2 Website

The **website** (www.polyphem-project.eu) is of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of POLYPHEM as it serves as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project deliverables and outcomes. This portal provides content to the scientific communities, policy makers, professionals, academic and researchers, market actors, and general public.

The website includes information on the project scope, objectives and activities, partners and information on the dissemination activities and documents.

Figure 2 - POLYPHEM Official Website

The POLYPHEM website was frequently updated, and the content was expanded constantly during the project lifetime. The website includes the following features:

- Overview of the concept, objectives, the partnership, and the activities proposed within the project;
- Publishing of the project newsletters, technical papers, and information about coming events;
- News posts and general information on POLYPHEM activities and events;
- Link to social media: LinkedIn, Twitter, and other EU projects;
- Access to a secured (consortium members only) collaborative space for sharing information and documents.

2.1.3 Templates

A **Word template** for the deliverables, and a **PowerPoint template**, to be used by the partners for all presentations on POLYPHEM, were elaborated. In addition, a **Poster template** was created by CNRS for the dissemination in different events.

Figure 3 - POLYPHEM PowerPoint template

Figure 4 - POLYPHEM Poster template

Figure 5 - POLYPHEM Deliverable template

2.1.4 Acknowledgements to EC public funds

All publications based on work funded by the EC within the activities of the POLYPHEM project should acknowledge their affiliation to POLYPHEM and bear recognition of the EC funding. Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text: «***This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 764048.***»
- A disclaimer should be used for any documents coming out of the project and specify that: “***All information in this document only reflect the author’s view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.***”

2.2 CREATION OF COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

The POLYPHEM project informative dissemination materials included the produced material containing information of the project, such as the project overview, scope, and vision, together with the outcomes, achievements, and results of the project. Depending on the phase of the project during which each material was created, its content may differ. The informative material which belongs to this category are:

- The brochures
- The project factsheet
- The project posters
- The infographic timeline
- The media press kit
- The videos
- The project website news
- The project newsletters

2.2.1 Brochures

During the POLYPHEM project lifetime, **2 brochures** were created.

The first POLYPHEM brochure was created at Month 6. The brochure was a multi-page document (4 pages) that contained general and straight-to-the-point information on the project. The main objective was to provide to all POLYPHEM audiences with a clear and attractive written overview of the project, and a summary of the main project objectives and characteristics. This brochure was designed to reach not only experts, but also interested non-specialists.

Figure 6 - POLYPHEM First brochure

Each partner has received a set of printed versions to distribute, and 50 copies were distributed at the second project meeting. Moreover, an electronic format of the brochures is available on the Website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/10/19/the-polyphem-brochure/>

A second version of the brochure was implemented at Month 40. This 7-page publication presents:

- An introduction to Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) as a technology to tackle climate change,
- The POLYPHEM project in a nutshell, its concept and innovations,
- The funding of this collaborative Horizon 2020 project by the EU, its main characteristics and a « big picture » of the Consortium,
- The technical work plan of the POLYPHEM project in terms of research, integration, manufacturing, testing and cross-cutting activities,
- The timeline and key achievements of the project,
- The expected impacts (technology, European, economic, environmental, and social).

Figure 7 - POLYPHEM Final brochure

Each partner has received a set of printed versions to distribute (100 each) and a further 100 brochures were distributed in December 2021, at the ENLIT conference, in Milan (Italy).

Also, an electronic format of the second brochure is available on the Website: https://www.polyphem-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/POLYPHEM_Brochure_Print.pdf

2.2.2 The project factsheet

To get a more detailed overview of the project activities, a **project factsheet** was created under the invitation of the European Commission at the beginning of the project and can be used for dissemination purposes. This was part of the dissemination material package that the partners could use to disseminate information on the project.

Figure 8 - POLYPHEM Project Fact Sheet

The project factsheet is available for download on the website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/09/07/polyphem-project-factsheet/>

2.2.3 The project posters

As part of the dissemination actions, **4 posters** were created to be used for exhibitions and other events. The posters are generic posters and can be used as such by all partners of the project.

OBJECTIVES

TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL-SCALE CONCENTRATED SOLAR POWER (CSP) PLANTS AND THEIR FLEXIBILITY TO GENERATE POWER ON DEMAND.

A NEW TECHNOLOGY IS PROPOSED: A SOLAR-DRIVEN COMBINED CYCLE WITH INTEGRATED THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE.

OUTCOMES

THE CONSTRUCTION OF A 60 KW PROTOTYPE PLANT WITH A 1,3 MWH THERMAL STORAGE UNIT AND THE VALIDATION OF THIS INNOVATIVE POWER CYCLE IN A RELEVANT ENVIRONMENT (TRL 6), AT THE THEMIS SOLAR TOWER IN TARGASSONE, FRANCE.

PROJECT WORKPLAN

RESEARCH

- WP1: 60kW SOLAR PROTOTYPE
- WP2: 1.3 MWH THERMAL STORAGE
- WP3: 60kW SOLAR PROTOTYPE
- WP4: 1.3 MWH THERMAL STORAGE

INTEGRATION

- WP5: INTEGRATION
- WP6: INTEGRATION
- WP7: INTEGRATION
- WP8: INTEGRATION

MANUFACTURING

- WP9: MANUFACTURING
- WP10: MANUFACTURING
- WP11: MANUFACTURING
- WP12: MANUFACTURING

TESTING

- WP13: TESTING
- WP14: TESTING
- WP15: TESTING
- WP16: TESTING

CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITIES

- WP17: CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITIES
- WP18: CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITIES
- WP19: CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITIES
- WP20: CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITIES

PROJECT CONCEPT

Concentrated Solar Energy → All Brayton Cycle → Thermal Energy Storage → Organic Rankine Cycle → Power Generation on demand

Optional: Heating, Cooling, Desalination

PROJECT IMPACT

- ENERGY STORAGE:** Annual 100h Heat Generation, Annual 100h Electricity Generation
- DESALINATION:** Fresh Water Production
- GREEN HOUSES:** Sustainable Agriculture and Food Production
- ENVIRONMENTAL SAVINGS:** Reducing CO₂ emissions

POLYPHEM PROJECT DATA

CONSORTIUM
9 PARTNERS - 5 COUNTRIES

BUDGET
4,975 MILLIONS €

DURATION
48 MONTHS

START END DATE
01/04/2018 - 31/03/2022

PROJECT CALL
Developing the next generation technologies of renewable electricity and heating/cooling

CONTACT
alain.ferriere@promes.cnrs.fr

PARTNERS: CNRS, AALBORG CSP, Arraela, cea, Fraunhofer, KREPER, orcan, euronovia, CSEM, IRETH, Fraunhofer ISE

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 764048

The first one was created in July 2018 for the popularization event ESOF in Toulouse and was updated for the final infoday (with the updated dates related to the amendment).

Figure 9 - POLYPHEM Poster 1

Figure 10 - POLYPHEM Poster 2

Two other posters were created in June 2019 (for the smart energy conference in Paris – French poster version) and another one in July 2019 (for the CSP plaza conference in China – English poster version as below), both being combined to another H2020 project (ORC-PLUS), since the exhibition booth was a joint exhibition of these two projects, as dealing both of them with small scale CSP plants.

Figure 11 - POLYPHEM Poster 3

The last one was created in June 2022 for the Final Info Day, event hosted by CNRS at Themis in Targasonne and online.

2.2.4 Infographic timeline

The **visual timeline** of the POLYPHEM project highlights the numerous achievements of the project and provide straight-to-the-point information in a format easily shareable on platforms like social media.

The first version was created in Month 40 and updated in Month 50. It was widely disseminated through the website and social media.

Figure 12 - POLYPHEM Infographic Timeline

2.2.5 Media Press kit

A **Media press kit** was produced during the final year to inform on the project with general information, more specific details on the project and data for the mass media (articles online, future events, ...). This contains:

- Information on CSP in general applied to POLYPHEM
- A presentation of the project
- Factual figures and Data on the project
- Report on Final Infoday
- Results of the project
- The timeline and short information on the next step
- The impacts
- A summary of the communication and dissemination actions and especially the selection of some press articles to showcase our presence online

Figure 13 - POLYPHEM Press kit (cover page)

Figure 14 - POLYPHEM Press kit (page 3)

2.2.6 Videos & Webinar

2 Videos and **1 Webinar** were released by the consortium to raise awareness of the project and disseminate the work done by the partners to all audiences. There are currently 3 videos content available online, receiving a total of **526** views.

Figure 15 - POLYPHEM 1st Presentation video

A **motion design video** was produced and spread on the website and social media. At the beginning, the video shows the importance of Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) technologies in the energy transition, how it works and its wide range of applications. Then, the video explains the POLYPHEM innovative technology and concept, its main objectives and expected applications and impact for the EU. Finally, it presents the Consortium and its main characteristics such as the budget received, number of EU member states engaged and the duration of the project.

So far, the video has 217 views.

URL: https://youtu.be/Lw_JCO8S734

With more than 90 participants, the first POLYPHEM **webinar** was presented jointly by our partners from CNRS-PROMES, CIEMAT-PSA, AALBORG CSP, and Fraunhofer ISE on 13 December 2021.

Addressing key concepts in Concentrated Solar Power technologies, its challenges but also its main opportunities, this webinar lasted 1 hour and 30 minutes, including a Q&A session towards our speakers.

So far, the video has 309 views.

The video is available in replay here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RLgRmA3tknU&feature=youtu.be>

Presentations made during this webinar are available in open access here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/01/13/watch-the-polyphem-webinar-on-small-scale-csp-challenges-opportunities/>

A **final project video** replaced the initial interviews of the partners. The aim was to present the main results and achievements of the Consortium.

Therefore each institution presented its key results obtained during the project lifetime and the main challenges they faced.

Figure 16 - POLYPHEM Webinar on CSP challenges and opportunities

Figure 17 - POLYPHEM Final video on results

2.2.7 Website news

As part of the Website, the section **News** was filled regularly to provide information on project updates. This helped to link to the POLYPHEM website and intends to increase the website visits but also keeps the website

up to date.

News were published once per month approximatively with an increase of publications in the last reporting period due to the increase of activities in terms of dissemination and communication. During the course of the project, each partner contributed several times to this area by describing the progress of his/her activities, the project results and the benefit they gain out of their involvement.

The first news was published on the website in July 2018. So far, there has been 80 news.

With regards to the news page of the Website, our objective was to post at least one news per month to raise interest and traffic on the website. This objective was successfully reached since there is a total number of **80** news published online, as shown in the table in Annex 1. According to the stats of Google Analytics, the News section is the second one, after the homepage, to receive the most views.

2.2.8 Newsletters

To increase the dissemination of the news on the project and to maximize the impact and number of readers, instead of sending a separate Newsletter specific for the project, the project was using the H2020 CSP projects network and joint newsletter with other H2020 CSP projects.

At the second period of reporting, news were included so far in **4 Newsletters** (Nov 2018, April 2019, Nov 2019 and April 2020) from the H2020 CSP joint bulletin which is an initiative from H2020 CSP projects.

All editions can be accessible here and are downloadable on the website: <https://us15.campaign-archive.com/home/?u=be5a9e502ccb8c519b107bae4&id=048ceab545>

Figure 18 - H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter

However, now at the end of the project, **7 newsletters** were produced during the project. Due to the termination of the H2020 joint CSP projects' newsletter (which was coordinated by EUREC), POLYPHEM has developed its own newsletter from November 2021.

POLYPHEM Newsletter was disseminated to a wide network using the stakeholder database of more than 1750 contacts, reaching out to outside the POLYPHEM community.

Figure 19 - POLYPHEM Newsletter

All editions can be accessible and downloadable on the POLYPHEM website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/category/newsletters/>

3. PARTICIPATION TO EVENTS

3.1.1 Organisation of events

POLYPHEM organised 2 events, including:

Webinar on “Small-scale Concentrated Solar Power”, 13 December 2021: With more than 90 participants, the first POLYPHEM webinar was presented jointly by our partners from CNRS-PROMES, CIEMAT-PSA, AALBORG CSP, and Fraunhofer ISE. Addressing key concepts in Concentrated Solar Power technologies, its challenges but also its main opportunities, this webinar lasted 1hour and 30 minutes, including a Q&A session towards our speakers.

The replay is available here <https://youtu.be/RLgRmA3tknU> and the presentations are available for download here <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/01/13/watch-the-polyphem-webinar-on-small-scale-csp-challenges-opportunities/>

POLYPHEM
Final Infoday

Small Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

Market: Stages of development, Flexibility, Technical evolution to be competitive, Costs of technologies & components, What to expect from the technology in 10-30 years, Specific performance results.

Wednesday 6 July 2022
09:00 – 16:00 CEST
Hybrid event

Centre de la recherche CNRS | Tarascon, France
Free Registration [HERE](#)

Online | Zoom
Free Registration [HERE](#)

Logos: CNRS, cea, Fraunhofer ISE, AALBORG CSP, euronovia, KAEFER, orcan, ARRABELA

MORE INFORMATION
<https://www.polyphem-project.eu/>
c.berthod@euronovia-conisat.eu

On Wednesday 6 July 2022, the **Final Infoday** was an amazing opportunity to present and explain the main results of the project. On this occasion, partners delivered interesting presentations together with an enriching panel discussion. Finally, the Final Infoday was wrapped with a visit of the facilities.

The PowerPoint presentations are available here <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/07/27/polyphem-final-project-meeting-and-infoday/> and some pictures of the visit of the facilities are available here <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/dissemination/#gallery>

3.1.2 Scientific Conferences with peer-reviewed presentations and/or posters

Participation to **8 peer-reviewed scientific conferences** resulting in:

- **SolarPACES 2018** (2-5 October 2018, Casablanca, Morocco) – 2 papers were submitted and presented as poster
 - CNRS-PROMES: *POLYPHEM an Innovative Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle*
 - CIEMAT-PSA: *R& D on Thermal Storage in POLYPHEM Project*

All documents from these two presentations (abstract and poster) can be downloaded on the website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/10/16/polyphem-solarpaces-2018/>

- **SolarPACES 2019** (1-4 October 2019, Daegu, South Korea) – 2 papers submitted and presented as oral presentation
 - CIEMAT-PSA: *Prediction of Thermocline Zone Development at the Beginning of Dynamic Processes in Single Storage Tanks with Liquid Media*
 - Fraunhofer-ISE: *Design of an Experimental Prototype of a Solar-Driven CCGT Plant with Thermal Storage Based on an Existent Solar Power Tower Facility*

All documents from these two presentations (abstract, full paper submitted at the conference, PowerPoint presentation) can be downloaded on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/10/10/polyphem-solarpaces-2019/>

- **SolarPACES 2020** (Online) – 2 papers were submitted and presented as oral presentation
 - Fraunhofer-ISE: *Simulation-Based Comparison of Different Operating Strategies for a Dispatchable Solar-Driven*
 - CIEMAT, ARRABELA: *Thermal Storage Filler Material Distribution for the Polyphem Project*

All documents from these presentations (abstract and poster) can be downloaded on the website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/10/08/presentation-solarpaces-2020/>

- **SolarPACES 2021** (Online) – 1 paper was submitted and presented as poster

- Fraunhofer-ISE: *Techno-Economic Performance Analysis of a CSP-Driven CCGT with Stratified TES at Various DNI Levels and Demand Conditions Based on Transient Simulation*

All documents from these presentations (abstract and poster) can be downloaded on the website: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/08/conference-proceedings-solarpaces-2021/>

- **SolarPACES 2022** (27-30 September, Albuquerque, USA) – 1 paper was submitted and presented as poster
 - CIEMAT, CNRS, ARRAELA: *Thermocline storage tank with concrete filler: Lessons learnt during the commissioning and first experimental results of the POLYPHEM project*

All documents from these presentations (abstract and poster) will be available for download on the website as soon as they are published.

3.1.3 Scientific and industrial exhibitions

POLYPHEM participated in **6 scientific and industrial exhibitions** resulting in:

- **CSP plaza** (10-12 July 2019, Suzhou, China) - POLYPHEM took part in the CSP Plaza Conference that was held in Suzhou, China, from 10 to 12 July 2019. POLYPHEM had a booth and it was a good opportunity to promote the project in an international environment in Asia to high-level CSP experts. This meeting gathered more than 800 people coming from all over the world showcasing 60 exhibitions and 50 speeches. Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/07/23/csp-plaza-conference-2019-china/>

Figure 20 - POLYPHEM at CSP Plaza 2019, Suzhou (CN)

- **ORC Power Systems** (9-11 September 2019, Athens, Greece) - POLYPHEM participated in the 5th edition of the ORC Power Systems Conference, that took place in Athens, Greece on 9-11 September 2019. The project was featured with a roll-up poster in the EU Corner zone presented by POLYPHEM partner Orcan Energy. The 2019 edition of the International ORC Conference gathered nearly 300 participants from 33 countries and more than 120 presentations. Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/09/13/orc-power-systems-conference-2019/>

Figure 21 - POLYPHEM at ORC Power Systems 2019, Athens (GR)

- SolarPACES 2019** (1-4 October 2019, Daegu, South Korea) – POLYPHEM was featured in a joint booth in the exhibition area of the conference with other CSP projects funded under Horizon 2020, which gave us the opportunity to further network and present the project to interested participants. Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/10/10/polyphem-solarpaces-2019/>

Figure 22 - H2020 CSP Joint Booth at SolarPACES 2019, Daegu (SK)

- SolarPACES 2020** (28 September – 2 October 2020, Digital) - POLYPHEM team held a virtual booth that offered the possibility to meet partners interested in the project’s technology and strengthen our network. Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/10/08/presentation-solarpaces-2020/>

Figure 23 - POLYPHEM Virtual stand at SolarPACES 2020

- **SolarPACES 2021** (27 September – 1st October 2021, Digital) - POLYPHEM team held a virtual booth that offered the possibility to meet partners interested in the project’s technology and strengthen our network. Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/05/update-polyphem-at-solarpaces-2021/>

Figure 24 - POLYPHEM Virtual stand at SolarPACES 2021

- **ENLIT 2021** (30 November – 2 December 2021, Milan, Italy) – Enlit Europe is the new unifying brand for European Utility Week & POWERGEN Europe which showcases expert knowledge, innovative solutions and foresight from industry leaders, to help shape Europe’s energy transition. This large annual event gathers thousands of participants each year. POLYPHEM had a virtual stand in the EU projects zone and it was a good opportunity for participants to access all the exhibitors’ stands and to keep exchanging with interested participants. Also, POLYPHEM team shared a pod in the EU projects zone together with other H2020/Horizon Europe projects working in the European Energy landscape. We showed the project presentation video, as well as brochures for the public (academics and industries). Information can be found on the website here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/15/polyphem-at-enlit-europe-2021/>

Figure 25 - POLYPHEM at ENLIT 2021, Milan (IT)

3.1.4 Generic events and exhibitions

Participation in **2 generic events** on renewable energy resulting in 2 oral presentations as follows:

- **JNES** (27-29 June 2018, Lyon, France) - The 5th edition of the National Days on Solar Energy (Journées Nationales sur l'Énergie Solaire – JNES) took place from 27th to 29th June 2018 at the LyonTech Campus in Villeurbanne, France. This annual congress aims at presenting a broad spectrum of research and technology state-of-play in the field of solar energy, including concentrated solar power. In this context, Alain Ferrière, POLYPHEM coordinator at CNRS-PROMES, presented the main objectives, innovation and expected results. The presentation in French can be downloaded here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/09/20/presentation-polyphem-jnes-2018/>
- **Sustainable Places** (4-7 June 2019, Cagliari, Italy) - The 7th edition of the Sustainable Places conference took place from 4th to 7th June 2019 in Cagliari, Italy. This annual conference aims at promoting the dissemination of research, collaboration, networking and the creation of market opportunities in the field of building sustainability. In the context of the 2019 edition, the NEXTOWER project organised a workshop on the “New generation of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) Technologies” with the participation of other H2020 funded projects, including POLYPHEM. On this occasion, POLYPHEM coordinator Alain Ferrière (CNRS) presented the main objectives and the results achieved during the 1st year of the project. POLYPHEM was also featured in the conference proceedings of Sustainable Places 2019.

Figure 26 - POLYPHEM at Sustainable Places 2019, Cagliari (IT)

Information can be downloaded here: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/06/13/polyphem->

[sustainable-places- 2019/](#)

Participation to the INEA H2020 CSP events internal to H2020 CSP projects only

- **INEA H2020 coordinators’workshop on CSP**, 26 June 2018, Brussels, Belgium - On 26th June 2018, the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) hosted the second H2020 Coordinators’ Workshop on Concentrated Solar Power. The aim of the workshop is to investigate potential synergies between projects in the area of Concentrated Solar Power with ongoing RIA, IA and CSA projects. POLYPHEM project presentation was made by Alain Ferrière, who also participated in the group discussions to identify potential synergies and overlaps.

Figure 27 - POLYPHEM at INEA H2020 Coordinators workshop on CSP 2018, Brussels (BE)

- **INEA H2020 coordinators’workshop on CSP**, 26 November 2019, Brussels, Belgium - Alain Ferrière attended the 3rd H2020 CSP Workshop on the 26th of November, which took place in the INEA premises in Brussels. Participants had the chance to exchange views on the contribution of H2020 CSP projects and the policy elements required for the reinforcement of the CSP sector.

Figure 28 - POLYPHEM at INEA H2020 Coordinators workshop on CSP 2019, Brussels (BE)

Participation to 2 generic exhibitions open to public resulting in 2 joint booths.

- **ESOF** (9-14 July 2018, Toulouse, France) - The 8th edition of ESOF (Euroscience Open Forum) took place on 9-14 July 2018 in Toulouse, France. This bi-annual conference is one of the biggest interdisciplinary popularization event for science in Europe. It gathers scientists, young researchers, entrepreneurs and innovators, policy makers, science communicators and the general public from all over Europe. POLYPHEM participated in the 2018 edition through a shared booth with two other H2020 CSP projects. Also, the POLYPHEM team created a special poster that was exhibited during the 5 days of the event, presenting the project’s objectives and impact to the general public.

Figure 29 - POLYPHEM at ESOF 2018, Toulouse (FR)

Information can be downloaded here:

<https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/08/02/polyphem-at-esof/>

- **Smart Energy Expo** (17-18 June 2019, Paris, France) - POLYPHEM took part in the Smart Energy Expo conference, that was held in Paris, France on 17 & 18 June 2019. We shared a booth with two other H2020 CSP projects, which was a good opportunity to network and promote POLYPHEM among energy experts from a wide range of sectors. Also, Euronovia – POLYPHEM partner for dissemination and communication activities – introduced the project within a general presentation about H2020 calls for proposals. The 2019 edition of Smart Energy Expo gathered more than 3500 participants, 140 speakers, 80 exhibitors and 96 workshops.

Figure 30 - POLYPHEM at Smart Energy Expo 2019, Paris (FR)

- In addition to these events, Euronovia has participated to 2 major conferences in the field of solar

energy and electricity generation (The **Solar World Congress** in November 2019 in Chile and the **Powergen-European Utility Week** conference in November 2019 in France), as part of other EU projects' actions. However, seeing the strong interest that the participants of these two conferences could have had for POLYPHEM, flyers from the project were distributed there.

3.2 PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

3.2.1 Open access

As the European Union, POLYPHEM strongly support the Open access policy that is the practice of providing online access to scientific information, free of charge to the user and reusable. Therefore, all the scientific publications provided in the POLYPHEM framework were made available for free in Open access for all.

All publications are stored in the online repository “Zenodo”, in a dedicated community created for POLYPHEM and managed by CNRS and Euronovia: <https://zenodo.org/communities/polyphem/>

Figure 31 - POLYPHEM Zenodo Account

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable.

This platform has been chosen due to its strong integration with the OpenAIRE program. Indeed, as soon as a document is integrated into Zenodo, this is rapidly curated by OpenAIRE and put in CORDIS and the project participant portal.

So far, all deliverables, conference proceedings and scientific publications were deposited on the Zenodo platform. All other communication materials were also uploaded there, when relevant. It also contains research data (see section 3.4).

3.2.2 OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA

As part of the project, a **Data Management Plan (DMP)** was submitted in September 2018 to define the procedures needed to comply with the project obligation and Open Research data pilot. As the EC defines it, the data set to be put in open access are: “The Open Research Data Pilot applies primarily to the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications. Other data can also be provided by the beneficiaries on a voluntary basis.”⁹

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

The DMP outlines how the research data, collected or generated during the execution of the POLYPHEM project and after it's completion, will be handled. It describes what data will be collected/generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

This DMP was updated whenever necessary to include the details on the research data to put in open access and that have been processed or generated as part of the delivery of the project results. For each research data, the metadata was included in the DMP and deposited in the project repository Zenodo (see sub-section above).

A **POLYPHEM “Community”** (see Figure below) was created and, up to September 2022, **14 publications** (including deliverables) and **1 video** were published.

A list of **10 keywords** was established to enhance the visibility of the publications and enable linked requests : *Concentrated Solar Power, Decentralized Renewable Electricity Generation, Solar Energy, Themis Solar Tower, Solar Thermal Combined Cycle, Solar Thermal, Solarized Micro Gas-Turbine, Thermal Energy Storage, Solarized Organic Rankine Cycle, TES.*

Due to the late completion and commissioning of the Prototype plant, final data are not available yet but, further data will be published to later on, and the Zenodo platform will continue to be updated with, among others, the “Final results” video, the latest deliverables, the P&ID of the Project and Microsol-R dataset.

Figure 32 - POLYPHEM Community on Zenodo platform

3.2.3 POLYPHEM open access repository for open data

The **Zenodo platform**, as described in the section above was used to deposit each of the research data (including metadata described also in the DMP). For each research data, the following information was recorded in the open access repository:

- Information for **general record** in open access archive

Title* – Please list your preferred title for the dataset.

Creator(s) of the dataset* - Please list all researchers on the project and their institutional, college, school, department, or lab/center affiliation.

Kind of data¹⁰ including file format and size* -

Description* - Please provide a brief summary outlining the contents of the data file. Indicate the following as appropriate: purpose and scope; time period; areas of investigation; and any other special characteristics. Also indicate the number of data files, including the README file.

Subject/Keywords*

Date data were made publically available*

Access right – Open access, embargoed access, restricted access, closed access

Funders – European Commission – Horizon 2020 programme

Grant numbers - 764048

Publications related to dataset - Include full citation (e.g. DOI) to articles published based on these data or related to these data.

- If necessary, a **README** file should be deposited together with the data deposited there in order to explain clearly to the users how to easily use the data. This README file should contain if possible how the data was acquired and processed.

The methodology and technique used in collecting and creating the data;

The methods/modes of data collection (for example):

- The instruments, hardware and software used to collect the data
- Digitisation or transcription methods;
- Data collection protocols;
- Sampling design and procedure;
- Target population, units of observation.
- Describe your workflow and specific tools, instruments, procedures, hardware/software or protocols you might have used to process the data

3.2.4 Journal articles

3 papers were published in open access in the **Solar Energy journal** (ELSEVIER editor)

- Fraunhofer-ISE: *Optimization of Solar Tower molten salt cavity receivers for maximum yield based on annual performance assessment*
Authors: Peter Schött, Gregor Bern, De Wet van Rooyen, José Antonio, Fernández Pretel, Thomas Fluri, Peter Nitz
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.02.007> Volume 199, 15 March 2020, Pages 278-294
- CEA, CNRS: *Emissivity at high temperature of Ni-based superalloys for the design of solar receivers for future tower power plants*
Authors: Marianne Balat-Pichelin, Jean-Louis Sans, Eric Bêche, Ludovic Charpentier, Alain Ferrière, Sébastien Chomette
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111066> Volume 227, 1 August 2021, 111066
- CEA, CNRS: *Erratum to ‘Emissivity at high temperature of Ni-based superalloys for the design of solar receivers for future tower power plants’ [Solar Energy Mater. Solar Cells, 227, (2021), 111066]*
Authors: Marianne Balat-Pichelin, Jean-Louis Sans, Eric Bêche, Ludovic Charpentier, Alain Ferrière, Sébastien Chomette

¹⁰ text documents, spreadsheets, laboratory notebooks, field notebooks and diaries, questionnaires, transcripts and codebooks, audiotapes and videotapes, photographs and films, examination results, specimens, samples, artefacts, slides, database schemas, database contents, models, algorithms and scripts, workflows, standard operating procedures and protocols, experimental results

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111228> Volume 230, 15 September 2021, 111228

3.2.5 Conference proceedings

6 peer-reviewed **conference proceedings** were published.

- Following the **SolarPACES conference 2018**, a peer-reviewed conference proceeding was published.
 - CNRS-PROMES: *The POLYPHEM project: An innovative small-scale solar thermal combined cycle*
Authors: Alain Ferriere, Sebastien Chomette, Esther Rojas, Juan-Manuel Caruncho, Thomas Fluri, Daniel Ipse, Richard Aumann, Marie Prouteau, and Jens Jorgen Falsig
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117534>
 AIP Conference Proceedings 2126, 030022 (2019); Published Online: 26 July 2019
- Following the **SolarPACES conference 2019**, a peer-reviewed conference proceeding was published.
 - CIEMAT: *Prediction of Thermocline Zone Development at the Beginning of Dynamic Processes in Single Storage Tanks with Liquid Media*
Authors: Bayón, Rocío; Rojas, Esther
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0028900>
 AIP Conference Proceedings 2303, 190001 (2020); Published Online: 11 December 2020
- Following the **SolarPACES conference 2020**, a peer-reviewed conference proceeding was published.
 - Fraunhofer-ISE: *Simulation-Based Comparison of Different Operating Strategies for a Dispatchable Solar-Driven CCGT Plant with Stratified Thermal Storage*
Authors: Shahab Rohani, Francesco Sasso, Martin Karl, Peter Schöttl, Pedro Rubio Cifuentes, Thomas Fluri
- Following the **SolarPACES conference 2021**, a peer-reviewed conference proceeding was published.
 - Fraunhofer-ISE: *Techno-Economic Performance Analysis of a CSP-Driven CCGT with Stratified TES at Various DNI Levels and Demand Conditions Based on Transient Simulation*
Authors: Pedro Rubio, Shahab Rohani, Maitane Ferreres, Tatvakumar Bhanderi, Julius Weiss, Peter Schöttl, Alain Ferriere and Thomas Fluri

Another conference proceedings was published without being peer-reviewed.

- Following the Sustainable Places conference, a paper gathering all contributions from the CSP workshop was published. This is not a scientific paper.
Next Generation of Concentrated Solar Power Technologies
Authors: Tatiana Loureiro, Raymond Sterling, Claudio Testani, Elena Torralba-Calleja, Luca Turchetti, Manuel Blanco, Alain Ferriere and Fabrizio Perrotta
 Proceedings 2019, 20, 7; doi:10.3390/proceedings2019020007

3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

3.3.1 Twitter

In order to join forces with other H2020 CSP projects, and not just have one account for one project (which would decrease its potential to gather followers), a joint twitter account has been created by Euronovia to feature CSP Projects funded under H2020 projects: <https://twitter.com/H2020CSP>

At **Month 24**, there were **207 followers**.

Figure 33 - H2020 CSP Twitter joint account

Examples of Twitter posts published on the joint account and featuring the project at Month 24:

Figure 34 - POLYPHEM Twitter posts (Month 24)

At the end of the project (Month 53), it has now **396 followers**, which demonstrates a considerable increase and a certain interest towards CSP. Below some examples of Twitter posts published on the joint account and featuring the project at Month 53:

Figure 35 - POLYPHEM Twitter posts (Month 53)

3.3.2 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn page was created. At **Month 24, 105 members** were behind the POLYPHEM LinkedIn group, whose aim is to widespread on the social network the information about the project: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/18696825/>

The final aim was to reach 200 followers by the end of the project according to original KPIs fixed.

Examples of LinkedIn posts featuring the project:

Figure 36 - POLYPHEM LinkedIn posts

At **Month 53, 210 members** were behind the POLYPHEM LinkedIn group, which has significantly increased since the last deliverable update and overpassed the initial target objective.

In addition to the POLYPHEM own LinkedIn page, a joint LinkedIn account has been created by another H2020 CSP project. This can be found here: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13519618/>. Whenever relevant, POLYPHEM is featured there also, together with other H2020 CSP projects.

3.4 ARTICLES ON THE WEB

3.4.1 Press releases

Up to now, **one press release** has been published and spread to our own Media database. Indeed, at Month 27, a media monitoring and press watch related to articles on small scale CSP (objective – to build a press contact database) was conducted. More than **150 entries** have been listed among which more than **60 articles** dealing with small-scale CSP.

Figure 37 - POLYPHEM Press Release (page 1)

Figure 38 - POLYPHEM Press Release (page 2)

Two were normally planned during the project but only one was launched as soon as the project has showcased results that are of interest for the press, here at the very end of the project.

3.4.2 Articles in specialized magazines

So far, **3 articles** have been published in specialized magazines.

2 were published in the **European Energy Innovation magazine**, a renowned communication platform designed with one purpose in mind: to put energy and transport stakeholders in touch with each other.

Figure 39 - POLYPHEM in EEI Autumn 2021 edition

In the European Energy Innovation **Autumn 2021 edition**, the POLYPHEM project appeared notably in « The contribution of EU funded projects to support the clean energy transition of EU companies » in the third part related to the « Clean energy transition ». This article explains the challenges the POLYPHEM project aims to respond to, its main characteristics and objectives, and finally, its expected impacts and results.

Link: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/09/29/polyphem-article-in-european-energy-innovation-magazine/>

Figure 40 – POLYPHEM Article in EEI Autumn 2022 Edition

In the European Energy Innovation **Autumn 2022 edition**, the POLYPHEM will presents its key achievements, the challenges partners faced during the project lifetime and the impact of the results achieved.

Link: *To be available soon*

Figure 41 - POLYPHEM interview in EU Projects Zone Podcast series 2021

In the context of the **ENLIT Europe 2021**, Alain Ferriere from the CNRS was invited to participate in one episode of the *EU Projects Zone Podcast Series* to present the POLYPHEM project. There is a written and a podcast version of the interview that lasts around 15 minutes.

Link to the article and podcast: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/05/16/enlit-2021-eu-project-zone-podcast-interview-with-alain-ferriere/>

3.4.3 Media online presence

So far, **15 articles** can be found on the internet in open access and related to POLYPHEM:

- One directly written by **KAEFER** in their **annual public company magazine** that is published worldwide in 6 different languages: <https://www.kaefer.com/Binaries/Binary1545/K-WERT-Nr.36-EN.pdf>

- One written by the **CSP Chinese industrial association CSP Focus** and related to one of the POLYPHEM news published onto our website: http://www.cspfocus.cn/en/market/detail_2324.htm

Another article has been published in a **French local bimonthly magazine “Pyrénées Magazine”**¹¹ that

Figure 39 - POLYPHEM in Pyrénées Magazine

published a dossier on the PROMES-CNRS lab, hence featuring Themis and the POLYPHEM project. However, since the focus is on regional distribution, and the magazine had to be bought in a local shop, the dissemination is not as interesting as expected and up to now, this would not be included in the counting.

- One directly written by **KAEFER** in their **annual public company magazine** entitled “‘Polyphem’ – How two KAEFER engineers are planning to change the world!” that is published worldwide in 6 different languages: <https://www.kaefer.com/Binaries/Binary1545/K-WERT-Nr.36-EN.pdf>
- One page dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by **EURO** in the **Rural Digital Europe Platform**: https://rural-digital-europe.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::d643a2d1728f34726aa3d9c86ed31924
- One page dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by **Euronovia** in the **CINEA Brochure**: <https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/03/polyphem-presentation-in-cinea-brochure/>
- One paragraph dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by CNRS in the Themis page of the Wikipedia website: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Themis_\(solar_power_plant\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Themis_(solar_power_plant))
- One page dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by **Euronovia** in the **CORDIS** page of the European Commission: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/764048/fr>
- One page dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by **Euronovia** in the **Knowledge Center on Organic Rankine Cycle - KCORC**: <https://www.kcorc.org/en/rd-projects/polyphem/>
- One page dedicated to the POLYPHEM project by **Euronovia** in the **UMI Community Platform**: <https://community.umi.us/publication/5ea0029f2923d0869acc84c5>

¹¹ https://www.pyreneesmagazine.com/archives/sommaires-le-magazine/pyrmag-182-mars-avril-2019/copy28_of_pyrenees-mag-ndeg144

Table 7 - POLYPHEM Dissemination and Communication logbook**4.2 EVALUATION OF THE DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS**

During the POLYPHEM lifecycle, two mechanisms were used to review the progress of the dissemination activities and provide feedback to the project:

- Key Performance Indicators,
- The reports regarding the dissemination activities (planned deliverables in the DoA).

Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) are a measuring factor for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. Different KPIs are defined specifically for the communication activities.

They were used to assess the performance of the dissemination activities all along the project duration and reorientate the dissemination plan if necessary, when KPIs were not matched, and the expected impact not reached.

A tracking process was also implemented internally at Euronovia to ensure that all ongoing activities integrate Key Performance Indicators to measure the impact of these dissemination and communication activities.

Euronovia's communication manager was in charge of listing and tracking all the communication and dissemination activities of the partners. Regularly, partners were contacted to collect all information on the activities carried out by each of them (see Annex 2).

For each of the actions mentioned in the logbook, a new table was filled to evaluate the impact of the action and to analyse with the partner implementing the action, if it has been successful, see Table below:

Actions	Metric	Objective to reach	Success				Actual (August 2022)
			Excellent	Good	Moderate	Weak	
Journal articles (peer-reviewed)	Number	8	≥ 12	≥ 8	≥ 4	< 4	3
Conference papers and proceedings	Number	6	≥ 12	≥ 8	≥ 4	< 4	8
Website	Visits (monthly)	50	≥ 250	≥ 150	≥ 50	< 50	1 534 visitors (on average)
Website news posts	Number	60	≥ 50	≥ 30	≥ 10	< 10	80
Newsletter	Subscriber	50	≥ 250	≥ 150	≥ 50	< 50	1772
Newsletter	Number	9	≥ 8	≥ 6	≥ 3	< 3	7
Twitter	Followers	200	≥ 200	≥ 150	≥ 50	< 50	400
LinkedIn	Members	200	≥ 200	≥ 150	≥ 50	< 50	210
Online presence - media articles	Number	Not numbered	≥ 20	≥ 10	≥ 3	< 3	15
Press articles	Number	2	2				2
Press releases	Number	2	2				1
Exhibitions	Number	3	≥ 5	≥ 3	≥ 1	< 1	6
Events organised	Participants	20-40	≥ 50	≥ 30	≥ 10	< 10	169
Number of events attended	Number	Not numbered	≥ 15	≥ 10	≥ 5	< 5	15
Videos	Views	200	≥ 250	≥ 150	≥ 50	< 50	526
Webinars	Participants	40	≥ 60	≥ 40	≥ 20	< 20	129

Table 8 - POLYPHEM Dissemination and Communication KPI's assessment

Despite the context of Covid-19, we can notice that the indicators measuring the performance of the communication and dissemination actions are good, mostly reaching Excellent and Good levels.

Concerning the number of **Scientific publications** in renowned journals, this indicator is weak because we

experienced multiple problems during the implementation of the project. These include Covid-19 and its restrictive measures, defective materials, delays in delivery of equipment, etc. Consequently, the results came late in the project life. However, we are confident that this indicator will progress after the end of the project as results are still in progress.

Although the target for the **Conference papers and proceedings** is already good, we are confident that we will achieve the Excellent threshold by the end of the year, as 8 have already been achieved, 2 are in preparation for the future SolarPACES conference which will take place in September 2022.

Due to the COVID-19 situation and the stop of the H2020 joint CSP projects' **newsletter** (which was coordinated by EUREC), this has resulted in some delays. As a mitigation measure, POLYPHEM has developed its own newsletter from November 2021.

Regarding our **Online presence**, same remark as the Scientific publications, the communication campaigns towards the general public and the media had to be done at the very end of the project. Undoubtedly, this indicator, which is already at the good level, will reach excellence in the coming months following the sending of the media press kit and press releases presenting the key results of the project.

5. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The Consortium was aware that activities to disseminate and exploit results from research and innovation are an integral part of Horizon 2020. Therefore, enhanced dissemination and exploitation are strategic matters for the success of the POLYPHEM project, Horizon 2020, synergies with other programmes and for the achievement of impact on society at large.

To raise awareness of the importance of exploitation among partners, an innovation potential market study was first conducted in 2019 and **3 dedicated seminars** were organised by Euronovia on 16 December 2019, 19 and 20 July 2022. The aim was to help the consortium in analysing different routes to exploitation and advise on Intellectual Property Rights.

The main conclusions of these analyses are summarized in the sections below.

5.1 FIRST INNOVATION POTENTIAL MARKET STUDY

First, to get insights into the potential of development of the POLYPHEM technology, a **digital market study** was carried out in 2019. The format of the market study, which was done essentially digitally, enables to lower the costs of this type of study (compared to a classical market study), while still being able to map and receive key important feedback from far more respondents to proceed with the analysis of the replies.

In total, 1925 professionals were contacted, 462 contacts visited the study questionnaire and 73 people replied.

The origins of the respondents is shown in the map below:

Figure 40 - POLYPHEM Market study - Origin of panel of professionals

This study aimed at understanding the potential of development of the technology related to different key information:

- The market needs
- The relevance of the POLYPHEM technology
- The differentiation
- The strengths
- The benefits
- The objections
- The competitors
- Other applications
- Overall assessment

The information that was delivered to the audience to be questioned is found below. Only straight-to-the-point information was provided to enable for a better response from the audience (too many details could prevent the audience from replying to the study).

- POLYPHEM Introduction
 - POLYPHEM improves the performance of small-scale Concentrated Solar Power plants and their flexibility to generate power on demand. Along with a high average conversion efficiency of 19% and a low environmental profile, the plant characteristics make the technology valuable in the future energy system, in particular in sunny regions where the electric grid is weak or non-existing.
- Technology advantages
 - A significant cost reduction for small scale CSP plants (CAPEX <5 €/W, LCOE 16.5 to 21 c€/kWh)
 - Flexibility to generate power on demand with the integration of Thermal Energy Storage
 - No water requirement for cooling of the CSP plants
 - A higher conversion efficiency than the state-of-the-art for small installed capacity
 - 100% solar electricity can be obtained thanks to the micro Gas Turbine allowing for solar-only operation mode
- Problems to be solved
 - Meeting the variable energy demand of a mini-grid in remote areas with a technology having a low environmental impact is challenging. Indeed, addressing the market of distributed power generation in remote areas through the development of low-cost, dispatchable and more decarbonized energy is becoming a crucial economical and societal challenge.

- The consumption of important quantities of water for the cooling of CSP plants is also another issue for the environmental profile of CSP plants. This is decisive in locations where water scarcity is a critical issue, like in sunny regions and desertic areas. New technologies should aim at reducing and eliminating the needs for cooling and integrate environmental solutions for a low consumption of water.
- The POLYPHEM Solution
 - With the thermal storage integrated to the innovative thermodynamic cycle, the POLYPHEM technology generates renewable electricity on demand. This combined cycle with micro gas-turbine and organic Rankine cycle goes far beyond the state-of-the-art in the proposed configuration:
 - The solar energy is converted to power in the gas cycle and the exhaust heat is stored in a thermal energy storage unit in-between the micro gas-turbine and the ORC.
 - This new concept of small-scale CSP technology provides flexible solar power and firm capacity for decentralized small-scale power generation in the range from 40 kW to 2000 kW. The project will develop and test a 60 kW innovative prototype plant integrating a 1,3 MWh thermal storage unit.
 - Thermal Energy storage is a decisive advantage that distinguishes CSP plants from highly variable renewable power generation technologies like photovoltaics or wind:
 - With the integration of thermal storage, POLYPHEM meets the requirements of a local variable demand of energy with a high average conversion efficiency of 19% and a low environmental profile with an investment cost target below 5 €/W.
 - Moreover, the water requirement for cooling purposes is completely eliminated with the POLYPHEM technology since the novel combined cycle eliminates the needs for cooling. Most technologies on the market can't offer this water saving solution.
 - Also, the developed technology is suited for heating/cooling purposes or for other applications driven by heat at constant rate, like water desalination.

Following this study, more detailed information was sent again to the respondents who have expressed an interest in getting more information on the project. This had enabled to gather the insights of relevant stakeholders for the WP8 “Assessment of the Deployment of the Technology Developed in the Project” and the related deliverable D8.1 “Report on the Market Analysis and Benchmarking with Competing Technologies” (WP8 Leader: FRAUNHOFER ISE).

This activity in the WP8 provided strong inputs for the further updates of the PEDR.

5.2 MARKET TEST STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING

Furthermore, the same year, to test the market interest for the POLYPHEM technology, a market test was launched through a platform dedicated to collect feedback from professionals on a global scale, according to keywords related to the POLYPHEM technology, and renewables in general, to get inputs from stakeholders outside the CSP community. In total **73 stakeholders** were mapped, gathering people from the industry world but also from the public sector. The list of contacts was added to the database for wide dissemination of our materials, when necessary.

Figure 41 - POLYPHEM Market study - Results

Here is an example of the stakeholders who has replied to the market test:

- TECNALIA Research & Innovation Greenway CSP
- NegaWatt Omexom- Vinci Energies Universidad de Guanajuato
- FRENELL GmbH
- TSK Electrónica y Electricidad Grupo Cobra
- Terrasol Geosolar Inc. Advanced Solar Voltaic SolarCreed B.V
- ACS-Cobra
- Desigenia S.L.Indisolar Products Pvt. Ltd Carbon Reduction Ventures Pty Ltd Siemens
- Mitsubishi Hitachi Power Systems Americas, Inc.
- LEITAT Technological Center Siemens
- International Energy Agency CENER
- SUNCNIM
- Azelio AB CSIRO
- Archimede Solar Energy

5.3 EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

5.3.1 Methodology

In order to raise awareness of the importance of exploitation among partners, Euronovia organised **3 dedicated seminars** in 2019 and 2022, led by external experts on exploitation of the project results.

During these workshops, POLYPHEM partners were trained on the importance of **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** and exploitation in general, and were presented several templates to be used to collect information about the KERs identified by the consortium: a research and commercialization roadmap, risk analysis, lean canvas.

At the end of the meeting, partners were given instructions to fill in the templates presented during the meeting to track the project results, and to send them for analysis to the expert. These tables were constantly updated during the project duration and were refined until a final list of exploitable results was agreed upon by the Consortium (see sub-section below).

5.3.2 Results

At the beginning of the project, in the Grant Agreement, POLYPHEM partners proposed a preliminary table presenting the expected results of the project, as well as pathways for exploitation and dissemination. Project activities and the research work done or to be done are considered in terms of KERs. KERs are results that have commercial and/or societal significance.

Type of results to be exploited commercially or non-commercially	Lead user, target group	Exploitation	Dissemination to ensure the exploitation
Creation of scientific data on HT pressurized air solar receiver, hybridization of μGT, concrete thermocline storage tank, HT heat exchangers, dynamic control of hybrid solar combined cycle: bibliographical library, dataset of lab-test results, design tools, models, numerical simulation tools.	Basic and applied Researchers, Engineers, Developers	Publication through websites, open databases, supports for lectures and courses at European level, patents...	Dissemination in open access, lectures, licenses on patents
Construction of a prototype plant	Design Engineers, companies	Further commercialization of the technology, creation of patent and know-how, IP	Dissemination in Industrial Conferences, participation to trade fairs
Report/deliverable on: materials selection, design of components, plant layout, control system, performance assessment, LCA of POLYPHEM plant	Basic/applied researchers	Publication of scientific papers, communications in international conferences	Participation to Scientific conferences to present the publications
Techno-economic assessment to prove the reliability and cost-effectiveness of the technology in the near term	Investment sector (private or public agencies)	Funding of the future research and development	Business workshops organized during the project with business stakeholders
Creation of new services on: measurement techniques, assembly of metallic materials, dynamic simulation and control of thermal processes, design of HT solar receivers, design of small scale solar power generation and co-generation plants	PhD students, post-doctoral researchers, engineers, technicians	Creation of start-ups	Support to the young researchers and engineers in the creation of start-ups
Report on cost analysis and positioning of the technology into the energy mix system	EU and national Policy makers	Participation and support to EU policies	Dissemination to policy makers through EU networks and EU associations
An LCA model for the POLYPHEM technology to present the negligible impact on environment.	The standardization sector and the environmental and societal sector	Inputs provided to standardization and to environmental associations	Participation to standardization activities

Table 9 - POLYPHEM Preliminary list of KERs

To go further in the mapping of the Key Exploitable Results and potential exploitable routes, the table below was sent to all partners before the end of each periodic report in order to update the PEDR and the potential exploitable results:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
No.	Exploitable result	Lead partner	Further project partners participating in the development of the Exploitable result	Owner/s	Who will exploit it	Potential exploitation form (patent or know-how or standardization or publication)	Potential way of exploitation (direct industrial use or assignment or licence agreement)
1.							
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6.							

In addition and in order to obtain more information on the potential related to the exploitable results, further details could be obtained via the use of the table below, also sent to all partners:

Title of the exploitable result	Provide below a short description
Description of the Result	
Innovativeness introduced compared to already existing Products/Services	
Unique Selling Point	
Product/Service Market Size	
Market Trends/Public Acceptance	
Product/Service Positioning	
Legal or normative or ethical requirements (need for authorisations, compliance to standards, norms, etc.)	
Competitors/Incumbents	
Early Adopters - First Customers	
Cost of implementation - bringing product/service to the "market" (before Exploitation)	
Time to market	
Foreseen Product/Service Price	
Adequateness of Consortium Staff	
External Experts/Partners to be involved	
Status of IPR: Background (type and partner owner)	
Status of IPR: Foreground (type and partner owner)	
Status of IPR: use the results from the Exploitation Form	
Partner/s involved expectations	
Sources of financing foreseen after the end of the project	

On 16th December 2019, a **one-day workshop** with an external expert on KER was organised in Brussels (Belgium) in order to prepare the KER Knowledge Portfolio. On the workshop programme, all participants agreed to work on:

- bringing the project partners to the same level of understanding in terms of exploitation and commercialization (presentations);
- setting up a list of KERs generated during the project;

The service and the virtual Exploitation Strategy Seminar (ESS) provided the participants with the opportunity to work on:

- 1) the identification/grouping of key exploitable results;
- 2) the first definition of the related use mode;
- 3) the identification and mapping of risks related to the exploitation;
- 4) follow-up actions.

The ESS for POLYPHEM was organised on 19 - 20 July 2022 and conducted remotely, online.

On the first day, the Expert has reminded the Objectives of the European Commission, Objectives of the seminar, then made a Presentation of the whole process, what can we consider as an “exploitable result”?, walk-through the ESS compilation form. After this general introduction, the Consortium together with the Expert had proceeded to the updating of the potentially exploitable results and identification of the dependencies between the exploitable results (plenary), and setting/updating the PEDR. Finally, they had finished this first day with a full analysis of the first selected KER in terms of description, characterisation, roadmap, IP management, risk analysis, business dependencies and a consolidation between the risks analysis and the roadmap.

On day 2 of this seminar, the participants had run the same process for the two selected KERs.

Below is presented the final list of key exploitable results identified by the consortium, the main exploitable results being the POLYPHEM system prototype and the thermocline energy storage tank.

N°	Description of exploitable foreground	Lead
1	Validation of the mechanicals characteristics of diffusion bonding junctions between Nickel-based alloy parts for high temperature applications	CEA
2	Heavy duty gas turbine for different primary energies	KAEFER
3	POLYPHEM hybrid solar energy generation using flexible combined cycles	KAEFER
4	Predictive simulation model of a concrete thermocline storage tank with bricks as filler	CIEMAT
5	Improved ORC product with higher efficiency by increasing vapor temperature	Orcan
6	Numerical tool chain for design and optimization of CSP	Fraunhofer ISE
7	Concrete thermocline storage tank with bricks as filler	Arraela
8	Heat transfer coefficients for thermocline with stacked filler	CIEMAT
9	Replacement of ORC working fluid with a low GWP fluid	Orcan
10	Direct thermal oil input to ORC as alternative to hot water	Orcan

Table 10 - POLYPHEM Final list of KERs (1/2)

5.3.3 Recommendations from the expert

According to the expert, “Three KERs were considered at the online ESS” and “The discussion was very participative, with all the partners contributing. The seminar helped to focus on the main aspects to be considered in the future elaboration of the Final PEDR due at the end of the project’s life”.

Regarding the internal use of KER’s, the expert has considered that “the opportunity to use internally the solutions developed, to create a suite of innovative solutions to be offered on the market, is an advantage that the project partners are taking. Very well!”. Therefore, he strongly invited the Consortium to “continue updating them highlighting the competitive advantage that partners will gain over competitors.”

Also, regarding the planning towards the Exploitation plan, the expert recommended 6 suggestions:

- Keep it flexible enough and in line with the economic, environmental, societal and legal context in which the project has been set up;
- Use the lean canvas to better define early adopters, current solutions, unique value proposition and commercialisation channels for further information);

- Identify KPIs and milestones to define a roadmap, with all the activities needed to pave the way for use of the selected KERS ;
- Take into consideration the time and resources needed for implementing the next steps after the end of the project, considering that most of the partners have guidelines and procedures for spin-offs, joint ventures, licencing that require time.
- Consider consistency among the selected route to market, competition, early adopters, proposed exploitation actions and the expected impact of the project;
- Highlight the value chain dimension of the project and make sure this is considered to find the best set up in terms of future collaboration as partnership and as individual entities.

As when analysing the current results of the Risk Analysis at the project level, several inconsistencies has emerged between the risks identified of the different KERs. As an example, the actions projected for KER 3 & 4 are not covered in term of the validity of the statements, change in the environment, loss of expertise. Therefore and as it is crucial, the POLYPHEM consortium is aware and engaged to run the risks assessment as a Knowledge Management support such as explained during the seminars realised with the expert.

Then, the expert suggested that "if any KER [was aimed to be] jointly exploited by two or more partners, joint owners of KERs have to agree amongst themselves as soon as possible upon the detailed terms of exercising ownership and protection of such results in accordance and in proportion with the agreed intellectual contribution to its development." Here, the expert mentioned that "if relevant, bilateral/multilateral Memorandum of Understanding agreements should be signed among relevant partners."

In order to help the Consortium to do so, the expert offered a template for the MoU was provided enclosed to the final written report.

Last recommendations from the Expert from the Horizon Results Booster service:

- It is strongly suggested for Dissemination purposes to upload each Key Exploitable Result on the EC Horizon Results Platform <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>
- After the PDESC service has been delivered, it would be important to finalise the fruitful work done with Business Plan Development (BPD) and Go-to-Market services that can be requested at <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>
The aim of Go-to-Market services is to address one or more specific aspects for the implementation of the business/action plan:
 - Pitching (capacity to present in front of interested stakeholders)
 - IPR support (orientation in the IPR landscape)
 - Innovation Management (specialised training)
 - Exploitation options (exploration and in-depth analysis of the different options)
 - Business services (one among commercialisation plan, evaluation of business plan potential, creation of start-up)
 - Access to non-EU funding (analysis of funding options for follow-on financing)

5.3.4 Recommendations from the Innovation Advisory Board (IAB)

IAB Recommendations – July 2022

It is a pity to see that the project is so close to be completed and tested. However as there are not sufficient time and funding, we have the impression that there is a chance that the project will be ending without the chance of being properly commissioned and tested. Therefore, the IAB recommend to the EU committee to provide more time and funding to enable a proper closing, with testing of the project. This recommendation shall be seen in the light of the difficult conditions the project and all its team members has been faced with.

Interesting results. It is suggested to include the calculation and comparison of the LCOS for optimal design, instead of only use of LCOE. It will also be good to see how the comparison between different technologies is modified by usage of same pattern and location by each technology.

The IAB recommend that a comparison is modelled between “PV + Batteries” and “PV + Polyphem”

Seen in the light that PV produces Electricity during night and Batteries and Polyphem produces Electricity during night, however with the low temperature generated by Polyphem, also taken into account as a value stream of hot water, that will have a value for e.g. process heating and/or district heating and cooling. (This value is presently in Denmark between 50 to 150 Euro/KWh)

General recommendation: It is recommended that to avoid repetition of unintended situations/actions a record of all lessons learned shall be created as a public document.

October 2021

WP3

How does the different results of the TES modelling have impact on the global model of WP 7?

WP5

- o Receiver: Consider printing manufacturing of receiver modules.
- o What is used as benchmark of the cost of the receiver in WP8??

TES

Consider N2 blanket to ensure limited deterioration of Thermal Fluid. It is an important factor when evaluating the lifetime O&M cost of such plant. → *N2 Blanket to be considered*

WP6

It is recommended to add additional I/O channels as spares.

Time schedule

The time schedule of installation seems very optimistic. It is recommended that a dedicated person is appointed to make a *weekly one page small status follow up* on the progress and distribute to all involved partners. → *“Weekly one page status” to be set up shortly*

WP6

New system Overall start/Stop and Operation procedures and modes must be defined before testing and commissioning can start. It is recommended to make a written test program. Specially for the purpose of documenting that no contamination is happening from the filler material of the TES. At the end of the project the condition of the filler material of the TES must be inspected and documented. Also a procedure of plant recycling must be considered.

WP7

It is not clear if a simplified tool has been developed? It is still recommended to calculate some realistic business cases comparing of realistic alternative solutions.

NOV 2020

IAB find it important to see the results of erosion predictions for the filler as well as the other concrete items of the TES like walls etc. for an extended lifetime like 25 to 30 years. Has this been done and what is the result/prediction.

IAB is interested to see the expected lifetime cycle expectancy of the Gas-turbine. Has this been done and what is the result/prediction.

The IAB sees that the overall plant layout may not as a whole be able to compete with existing solutions on the free electrical market, however parts or subsystems may have a future role to play as part of a power plant. Pending more business case modelling.

Safety recommendation

Recommendation: IAB finds mandatory that the safety of the operation is investigated through the execution of an internal **HAZOP** (HAZard and OPerability analysis).

When dealing with flammable substances like thermal oil, there is a need to follow and to make investigations according to **ATEX EU Directive** (*Equipment and work space allowed in an environment with an explosive atmosphere*) must be evaluated and substantiated.

<p>April 2019</p> <p>Specification of the data handling: A specification of the data handling during operation and testing should be made. A list of expectations to dimension the measurement of data is needed (~1 page). The amount of measuring points needs to be evaluated.</p> <p>Notification of a delay: Notification of a delay seems to be under consideration. Strong Recommendation: a great effort to be put into searching a solution to avoid delays of the first deliverables, (enhanced work effort seeking possible manpower/resources)</p> <p>Specification and sharing of the shape of the filler materials: High priority has to be put into specification and sharing of the shape of the filler materials and also specifying the necessity of making further possible testing at Themis.</p> <p>TES connections : As TES will be constructed of concrete walls and bottom with the roof made of steel, strong focus if pipe connection through the concrete tank wall shall be made or if connections only should be through the top of the concrete TES tank.</p> <p>HTF/ TES Inlet & Outlet System: For inlet and outlet system of the HTF to/from the TES it is recommended that inspiration is sought from design of diffusors for Water tanks for thermocline operation.</p> <p>Delay for Subcontracting: It is underlined that major delay in some big components (receiver and oil/air HEX) is expected and time for subcontracting is long. Final design data must be provided to limit delay.</p> <p>Common Document A common document with ‘Components Specifications’ should be drafted, stored on the Intranet in WP4 and regularly updated.</p> <p>Philosophy of the future use of the model: In WP7, a model for future commercialization is developed. It should be adapted to country parameters (at least latitude, ...)</p>
<p>Oct 2018</p> <p>Design and Operation data: Give a big effort to get a complete set of design and operation data fixed.</p> <p>Each PARTNER should provide to the responsible partner (whoever that is) a range (MIN-MAX) values or in some cases providing two or more sets of data. Like the oil pressure with doubt of value 0 or 2 bar.</p> <p>P&ID: Operation philosophy (reformulated) For developing the correct P&ID, a document named ‘Operation Control/Philosophy’ should be developed describing start/stop and other procedures as well as normal operation. This also to determine the level of automation and exchange of signals with the solarfield.</p> <p>Each partner must provide their own control equipment or safety equipment, to be able to provide such from each partner, an ‘Overall Control architecture’ must be developed and distributed.</p> <p>TES capacity: TES capacity is understood to be specified at a range between 2- 2,6 MWh Modelling and simulation is recommended to be done in steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ First step can be done with benefit if it is done very fast and may be supporting of the determination of the operation parameters. It is suggested that a “global system performance simulation hypothesis and result” is shared at least at every main project meeting, starting as early as possible. ▪ At a later stage the other simulations will also take into account how the system will interact with a dynamic weak or strong grid. ▪ Finally, Partners should indicate if they will be interested to work with a simulation model with the aim of approaching customers to define how the technology shall be commercialized. <p>Scope of supply: The battery limits have been defined. Important to focus on the development of the P&I diagrams, Pipe, Instrument and valve lists for each partner should be gathered in a consolidated form provided by one responsible partner.</p>

5.4 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND IPR ISSUES

To help partners with this Knowledge Management and IPR issues, an internal event on “Exploitation and IPR” was organized by Euronovia for the partners of the project in collaboration with the IPR Helpdesk from the European Commission, who provides training for EU funded projects.

As part of the project, a Consortium Agreement has been signed to address all relevant issues related to IPRs and the results generated during the project (access rights to background and foreground necessary for the execution of the Project, rules for dissemination and use of own knowledge, etc). The Consortium Agreement (CA) complements the rules of the Grant Agreement.

In the Consortium Agreement, information on the following items are detailed:

- Which knowledge the consortium will exchange?
- Under which conditions?
- Who will be the owner of the results?
- What happens in cases of joint ownership?
- Who (and how) will exploit the results?
- Who (and how) will disseminate the results?
- How is the consortium protecting confidential information?

As a general rule, IPR is the property of those partners who have contributed to get the knowledge. The degree of ownership will depend on the degree of contribution to the IPR. This applies as long as it does not violate national legislation, specific agreements for scientific publication, and specific agreements among partners regarding ownership of IPR. Partners, that have jointly carried out work generating foreground and where their respective share of work cannot be ascertained, shall have joint ownership of that foreground and may establish appropriate joint ownership agreements or license agreements.

6. KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS AND EXPLOITATION ROUTES

Below is presented the final list of exploitable results identified by the consortium, the main exploitable results being:

Exploitable results	Owner(s) ; Joint ownership	Project partners who have related background	Form of exploitation, protection and its status	Who will exploit it	Starting TRL and final TRL level
Validation of the mechanicals characteristics of diffusion bonding junctions between nickel based alloy parts for high temperature applications	CEA	CEA, CNRS	Know how	Heat exchangers manufacturers, researchers	4 => 6
Heavy duty gas turbine for different primary energies	KAEFER	KAEFER	Secret know how, patent no possible, trade secret	KAEFER	3 => 5
POLYPHEM hybrid solar energy generation using flexible combined cycles	KAEFER	KAEFER	Secret know how, patent no possible, trade secret	KAEFER	4 => 5
Predictive simulation model of a concrete thermocline storage tank with bricks as filler	CIEMAT	CIEMAT, CEA, Fraunhofer, CNRS	Know-how but it will not be secret since the main aspects are expected to be published	CIEMAT	5 => 7
Improved ORC product with higher efficiency by increasing vapor temperature	Orcan	Orcan, KAEFER	Design	Orcan	6 => 8
Numerical tool chain for design and optimization of CSP	Fraunhofer	Fraunhofer, CIEMAT, ORCAN, KAEFER, CEA	Software, Design	Fraunhofer	5 => 7
Concrete thermocline storage tank with bricks as filler	Arraela	Arraela	Patent	Arraela	6 => 9
Heat transfer coefficients for thermocline with stacked filler	CIEMAT	NC	NC	NC	NC
Replacement of ORC working fluid with a low GWP fluid	Orcan	Orcan, KAEFER	Design	Orcan	6 => 9
Direct thermal oil input to ORC as alternative to hot water	Orcan	Orcan, KAEFER	Design	Orcan	6 => 9

Table 11 - POLYPHEM Final list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) – (2/2)

6.1.1 Follow-up funding opportunities

The aim of this chapter is to introduce and summarize the further funding opportunities both in private and public sector to secure the post-project future of the POLYPHEM initiative. It summarizes the other funding opportunities for the project partners who would like to further develop their results, or need financial help for commercialization, or would like to start a new R&D project in other fields, based on their results reached in this project. There are various possible alternatives to financing innovation projects from public and private sources. As it can be seen from the next picture, the choice of the proper source depends on the development phase of the project and also a good combination of them can be used throughout the life of the project.

Within public funding both regional and national funding schemes were monitored, as well as funding opportunities for spin-out research, further industrialisation and commercialisation support. Further investments will be needed for a wider implementation post-project, as it can be seen from the result descriptions and from the research roadmaps related to each result. In the following, we introduce and present the most common types of public and private sources for investment to be taken into consideration by the partners of the project.

6.1.1.1 Public grants

Public grants are set into motion by legislative bodies, greatly increasing the resources and accountability of the grant project. The amount of available money for public grants is usually greater than that of private grants, leading to overall larger awards. Additionally, a public grant is more likely to cover all the expenses of your project due to its size.

6.1.1.1.1 Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion. The programme facilitates collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges. It supports creating and better dispersing of excellent knowledge and technologies.

The main opportunities in Horizon Europe calls could be found in the **Cluster 5 - Climate, energy and mobility**. This cluster aims to fight climate change by better understanding its causes, evolution, risks, impacts and opportunities, and by making the energy and transport sectors more climate and environment-friendly, more efficient and competitive, smarter, safer and more resilient.

As POLYPHEM was a Research and Innovation Action project (RIA) the next step would be to apply for **Innovation Action** calls. The technology readiness levels of the results support this suggestion.

6.1.1.1.2 Other EU funds

- **European Investment Project Portal (EIPP):** The European Investment Project Portal (EIPP) is the EU matchmaking portal, enabling EU-based project promoters – public or private – to reach potential investors worldwide. Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/investeuportal/desktop/en/index.html>
- **The InvestEU Programme:** this programme aims to give an additional boost to sustainable investment, innovation and job creation in Europe. Link: https://europa.eu/investeu/home_en
- **Cascading grants:** It is a European Commission mechanism to distribute public funding in order to assist beneficiaries, such as start-ups, scale-ups, SME and/or mid-caps, in the uptake or development of digital innovation. Link : <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls>
- **University technology transfer offices (UTTOs)** often perform the function of transferring technology and commercialising innovations emerging from the University sector to the market place. Link: http://europa.eu/youreurope/business/funding-grants/access-to-finance/index_en.htm
- **Ad hoc grants for EIC Pathfinder and EIC Transition** grant holders
- **Fast Track scheme** to apply for the **EIC Accelerator**
- **EIC Transition:** The EIC Transition funding scheme builds on promising research results to demonstrate and mature the technology and develop business plans. Link: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-transition_en
- **EIC Accelerator:** The EIC Accelerator supports individual Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), in particular Startups and spinout companies to develop and scaleup game-changing innovations. Link: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator_en
- **EIC Prizes:** The EIC Prizes are awarded to whoever can most effectively meet a pre-defined challenge, without prescribing how that challenge should be solved.
- **EUREKA and Eurostars funding:** Eurostars supports international innovative projects led by research and development- performing small- and medium-sized enterprises (R&D-performing SMEs). Link: <https://www.eurostars-eureka.eu/>
- **Entrepreneurship and Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs):** The dedicated section on EU portal offers a wide focus dedicated to information on possible EU funding opportunities for SMEs and in general on what EU does for SMEs. Link: <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes>
- **Seal of Excellence – EuroQuity Initiative:** This initiative is dedicated to those companies who have received the Seal of Excellence from the EU Horizon 2020 SME Instrument Programme. Link: <https://www.euroquity.com/fr/community/Access4SMEs--Seal-of-Excellence-5bb56459-4f88-4d3c-a2eb-8e4b6e865ea5/>
- **Contracts and grants - access to business opportunities:** Several different contracts and grants are regularly made available for companies or organisations who want to work with Directorate General (DG) for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship, and SMEs or apply for funding.
- **Tenders Electronic Daily (TED):** TED provides free access to business opportunities from the European Union, the European Economic Area and beyond. Link: <http://ted.europa.eu/TED/search/search.do>
- **Innovaccess – Intellectual Property Portal:** Innovaccess aims to enhance Intellectual Property (IP) support services to Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to turn their Intellectual capital into commercial values and competitiveness. Link: <http://www.innovaccess.eu/>
- **European Green Deal:** The European Commission adopted a set of proposals to make the EU's climate, energy, transport and taxation policies fit for reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels. Link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- **European Institute of Technology and Innovation (EIT):** Under EIT's Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are partnerships that bring together businesses, research centers and universities.

- **LIFE Programme:** LIFE programme is the EU's funding instrument for the environment and climate action.
- **Dealflow:** This programme is sponsored by the European Commission to support EU-funded innovations with fundraising, venture building and networking. It supports EU-funded projects from H2020.
- **Accelerators and Incubators :** If the intention is to create a startup/spinoff, partners will check Accelerators/Incubators in their area. Examples of international and pan-European Accelerators/Incubators networks: Startup bootcamp, Startup weekend, StartupBus Europe, IMPACT Accelerator, Wayra. Examples of national Accelerators/Incubators: Denmark x Accelerace; France x TheFamily or Numa (Le Camping); Germany x Axel Springer Plug & Play, hub:raum; Netherlands x Rockstart; Spain x SeedRocket, Tetuan Valley
- **InnovFin:** EU Finance for Innovators is a joint initiative launched by the European Investment Bank Group (EIB and EIF) in cooperation with the European Commission under Horizon 2020.
- **Startup Europe:** STARTUP Europe is an initiative of the European Commission to connect high tech startups, scale-ups, investors, accelerators, corporate networks, universities and the media.
- **Interreg Europe:** A grant or a subvention is a direct financial contribution from the European Commission to support a specific action or project of a non-commercial nature, to cover eligible costs directly incurred by the beneficiaries. Link: <http://www.interregeurope.eu/>

6.1.1.2 Private investment

If a partner is about establishing a new company or wants to receive external funding in an existing company to finance product development, then private investment could be an option. Depending on the project phase and amount of money, different types of equity investors can be considered. Here we list the most common equity investment forms starting with earlier stage investors, which also means smaller amount of investment:

- Business Angel
- Venture capital funding
- Established companies – bank loan

6.1.1.3 Opportunities to guide post project exploitation

Horizon Results Booster

The above-mentioned **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** have commercial potential on the market, this is why we have planned to follow up on the exploitation opportunities using the **Horizon Results Booster** services. Horizon Results Booster is a package of specialized services to maximise the impact of Research & Innovation public investment and further amplify the added value of the Framework Programmes (FPs). It helps to bring a continual stream of innovation to the market and beyond. It will help to speed up the journey towards creating an impact, providing support to remove bottlenecks.

<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

Horizon Results Platform

We are also planning to upload our results on the Horizon Results Platform for the project's results to be more visible. The Horizon Results Platform is a Platform created by the European Commission where EU-funded

project consortia can present their results for search, contact owners, and hopefully form fruitful partnerships that will eventually generate the desired value. This way we hope to find additional funding, loans and investments, get help to reach the market, receive additional technical help, or join any kind of cooperation.

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/fundingtenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

7. CONCLUSIONS

The **communication and dissemination activities** during the project lifetime have been really satisfying, overstepping in some cases the project expectations, as demonstrated by the KPIs identified and monitored by the project. Several dissemination activities were undertaken and various tools were developed. All project partners have been actively involved in the dissemination of the project results by providing content and promoting the project through their website and contact networks.

Moreover, we made consistent use of social networks and online communication, especially in the last year and a half, when the Covid-19 pandemic has affected travels and meetings forcing us to cancel face-to-face meetings and participation in conferences. The dissemination of promotional material was also hampered, taking place principally online. However, thanks to online meetings and communication, we could develop close synergies with other EU projects in the field of CSP, increasing mutually our impact and developing a dynamic community interested in CSP technologies.

Also, while in the first three years we were able to organise and participate in many events and conferences. Unfortunately, two of our events that we were supposed to organise had to be cancelled. One in September 2019, to be organized by KAEFER in Bremen and in partnership with the university. However, it appeared that the date was not successfully chosen, and this was concomitant to German student exams. Another in April 2020, to be organized in Aalborg by Aalborg CSP in and in partnership with the university. But due to the COVID situation, the whole workshop had to be cancelled.

However, two events were organised online and in a hybrid format (online and face-to-face) to achieve the original objectives. The first, replacing the Technical workshop, was a webinar which gathered more than 90 participants and more than 300 views on YouTube; and the second, replacing the business workshop and the open info day, the Final Info day. This last hybrid event, both online and in person, allowed the project partners to present the results of the project, from an economic and environmental point of view to potential stakeholders. The day ended with a visit of the facilities. The event was attended by more than 30 participants, 26 online and 13 on site.

For what concerns **dissemination after the project ends**, the consortium members are committed to keeping the project website and project-dedicated social network tools updated for at least two years after the project completion. Furthermore, adequate IPR management and protection will be ensured after the project end-date.

When not confidential, all the main project findings and dissemination deliverables were made available through the Dissemination and Communication Database, along with all the dissemination activities/items, and shared with all main target groups as much as possible during and after the end of the project.

Also, both during and after the project end-date, the partners will liaise with other internationally relevant research groups and R&D projects on the same or related topics, thus exchanging good practices and ideas to take innovation further and eventually contributing to the further development and sustainable exploitation of the results.

The EU relevant institutions will be kept updated during and after the project through: a) participation of EU partners in EU-level workshops and Info-Days on themes related to the project; b) invitation of representatives of EU institutions to project events; c) sending of the project newsletter to contacts in such EU institutions; d) inclusion of these e-mail accounts in the project contact database.

In terms of the **exploitation of the results**, the consortium has identified a list of Key Exploitable Results and most of the project partners have ideas for further research and commercialization opportunities that could realize the transfer of the technologies into further research, funding, or market opportunities.

It is important to stress that at the POLYPHEM TRL level, commercial exploitation is not yet possible and further R&D and innovation investments are needed to bring the technology from TRL3 to TRL4 or TRL5.

Intermediate steps are necessary for the industrial development of the POLYPHEM concept. In particular, it is essential to solve technical issues, mainly on the solar receiver, in order to have the opportunity to validate the whole technology. Furthermore, for future large-scale commercialization, it is important to consider cogeneration of heat and power, as it offers more competitive opportunities.

Annexes

Annex 1 - POLYPHEM Website news

N#	Title	Item	Date	Link
1	Launch of the POLYPHEM project!	All news	03/07/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/07/03/launch-of-the-polyphem-project/
2	POLYPHEM presentation at the H2020 2nd coordinators' workshop on CSP	Events	10/07/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/07/10/polyphem-presentation-at-the-h2020-2nd-coordinators-workshop-on-csp/
3	POLYPHEM LOGO	Communication	18/07/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/07/18/polyphem-logo/
4	POLYPHEM at ESOF 2018	Events	02/08/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/08/02/polyphem-at-esof/
5	Deliverable 10.1: Management handbook	Dissemination	22/08/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/08/22/deliverable_10-1_management_handbook/
6	Deliverable 10.3: Project Management Plan	Dissemination	27/08/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/08/27/deliverable_10-3_project_management_plan/
7	POLYPHEM Project Factsheet	Communication	07/09/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/09/07/polyphem-project-factsheet/
8	Deliverable 10.2: POLYPHEM intranet	Dissemination	27/08/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/09/11/deliverable_10-2_polyphem_intranet/
9	Presentation of POLYPHEM at JNES 2018	Events	20/09/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/09/20/presentation-polyphem-jnes-2018/
10	POLYPHEM posters at SolarPACES 2018	Events	16/10/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/10/16/polyphem-solarpaces-2018/
11	The POLYPHEM brochure	Communication	19/10/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/10/19/the-polyphem-brochure/
12	Deliverable 9.1: Data Management Plan	Dissemination	09/11/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/11/09/deliverable_9-1_data_management_plan/
13	Deliverable 9.2: Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the project results (PEDR)	Dissemination	20/11/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/11/20/deliverable-9-2-pedr/
14	H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter – November 2018 edition	Newsletter	05/12/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/12/05/h2020-csp-projects-newsletter-november-2018-edition/
15	POLYPHEM article in KAEFER bi-annual international magazine	Communication	05/02/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/02/05/polyphem-article-in-kaefer-bi-annual-international-magazine/
16	POLYPHEM 3rd project meeting	Events	17/04/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/04/17/polyphem-3rd-project-meeting/
17	H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter – April 2019 Edition	Newsletter	19/04/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/04/19/h2020-csp-newsletter-april-2019/
18	7th edition of Sustainable Places – 2019	Events	29/05/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/05/29/7th-edition-of-sustainable-place/

19	POLYPHEM presentation at Sustainable Places 2019	Events	13/06/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/06/13/polyphem-sustainable-places-2019/
20	POLYPHEM at Smart Energies Expo 2019	Events	27/06/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/06/27/smart-energies-expo-2019/
21	POLYPHEM at the CSP Plaza Conference 2019 in China	Events	23/07/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/07/23/csp-plaza-conference-2019-china/
22	Scientific publications: Proceedings SolarPACES 2018 for POLYPHEM	Scientific Publications	01/08/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/08/01/scientific-publication-solarpaces2018/
23	POLYPHEM First Training Course (Cancelled)	Events	10/09/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/09/10/polyphem-first-training-course/
24	POLYPHEM at ORC Power Systems Conference 2019	Events	13/09/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/09/13/orc-power-systems-conference-2019/
25	POLYPHEM 4th Project Meeting	Events	20/09/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/09/20/polyphem-4-project-meeting/
26	POLYPHEM at SolarPACES 2019	Events	10/10/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/10/10/polyphem-solarpaces-2019/
27	The Polyphem history by KAEFER	All news	05/11/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/11/05/polyphem-history-kaefer/
28	Deliverable 3.1: Report on the design and specifications of filler, tank, and foundations	Dissemination	21/11/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/11/21/deliverable_3-1_report_design_and_specifications_of-filler_tank_foundations/
29	H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter – November 2019 Edition	Newsletter	04/12/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/12/04/h2020-csp-newsletter-november-2019/
30	POLYPHEM Review Meeting and Exploitation Workshop – December 2019	Events	20/12/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/12/20/review-meeting-exploitation-workshop-2019/
31	POLYPHEM presentation at INEA 3rd H2020 coordinators' workshop in CSP	Events	07/01/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/01/07/polyphem-presentation-at-inea-3rd-h2020-coordinators-workshop-in-csp/
32	POLYPHEM Workshop in Aalborg, Denmark (Postponed event)	Events	12/02/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/02/12/event-polyphem-workshop-aalborg/
33	Deliverable 2.1: Modification of coremodule solar-driven micro-gas-turbine	Dissemination	11/03/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/03/11/deliverable_2-1_modification_of_coremodule_solar-driven_micro-gas-turbine/
34	Periodic Reporting 1: Review of the first 18 months of POLYPHEM	Project Status	20/03/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/03/20/periodic-report-rp1/
35	Deliverable 2.2: Recovery Heat Exchanger	Dissemination	08/04/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/04/08/deliverable-2-2_recovery_heat_exchanger/
36	Deliverable 2.3: Turbine – Receiver Interconnection tubing	Dissemination	16/04/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/04/16/deliverable-2-3_turbine_receiver_interconnection_tubing/
37	H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter – April 2020 Edition	Newsletter	20/04/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/04/20/h2020-csp-projects-newsletter-april-2020-edition/

38	Deliverable 2.4: Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) board	Dissemination	29/04/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/04/29/deliverable_2-4_programmable_logic_controller_plc_board/
39	POLYPHEM 5th Project Meeting	All news	05/05/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/05/05/polyphem-5th-projectmeeting/
40	Scientific Publication: Optimization of Solar Tower molten salt cavity receivers for maximum yield based on annual performance assessment	Scientific Publications	12/05/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/05/12/scientific-publication-fraunhofer-ise-ises-2020/
41	Deliverable 3.2: Report on the design and specifications for the integration of the whole TES in the POLYPHEM system	Dissemination	20/05/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/05/20/deliverable_3-2_report_design_specifications_integration_tes/
42	Deliverable 4.1: Report on the overall plant layout	Dissemination	25/05/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/05/25/deliverable_4-1_report_on_the_overall_plant_layout/
43	POLYPHEM publications now available on the Zenodo platform	All news	25/06/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/06/25/polyphe-zenodo-open-access/
44	Keep up with the news from POLYPHEM on social media!	Communication	24/08/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/08/24/news-polyphem-social-media/
45	POLYPHEM at SolarPACES 2020	Events	22/09/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/09/22/solarpaces-2020-virtual/
46	POLYPHEM presentation at SolarPACES 2020	Scientific Publications	08/10/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/10/08/presentation-solarpaces-2020/
47	Deliverable 3.3: Report on Filler Material	Dissemination	15/10/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/10/15/deliverable-3-3-filler-material/
48	POLYPHEM 6th Project Meeting	All news	23/11/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/11/23/6-project-meeting-november-22/
49	Save the date: POLYPHEM at Enlit Europe 2021	Events	27/11/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/11/27/save-the-date-polyphem-at-enlit-europe-2021/
50	Deliverable 2.5: Report on the designed of the modified ORC system	Dissemination	03/12/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/12/03/deliverable_2-5_report_design_modified_orc_system/
51	Deliverable 1.1: Report on the benchmark of high temperature oxidation resistant materials and thermo-mechanical test campaign	Dissemination	09/12/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/12/09/deliverable_1-1_report-on-the-benchmark-of-high-temperature-oxidation-resistant-materials-and-thermo-mechanical-test-campaign/
52	Deliverable 1.2: Report on the solar receiver design optimization	Dissemination	15/12/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/12/15/deliverable_1-2_report-on-the-solar-receiver-design-optimization/
53	Deliverable 7.1: Report on Preliminary System Modelling	Dissemination	18/12/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/12/18/deliverable_7-1_report_preliminary_system_modelling/
54	H2020 CSP Projects Newsletter – January 2021 Edition	Newsletter	28/01/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/01/28/h2020-csp-projects-newsletter-january-2021-edition/

55	Conference proceedings : SolarPACES 2019	Scientific Publications	01/03/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/03/01/proceedings-solarpaces-2019/
56	POLYPHEM Project Meeting M36 - April 2021	All news	10/05/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/05/10/polyphem-project-meeting-m36/
57	Scientific Publication: Emissivity at high temperature of Ni-based superalloys for the design of solar receivers for future tower power plants	Scientific Publications	12/08/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/08/12/scientific-publication/
58	POLYPHEM at SolarPACES 2021	Events	15/09/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/09/15/polyphem-at-solarpaces-2021/
59	Meet the team: Discover the Work Package 1 with CEA	Dissemination	20/09/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/09/20/meet-the-team-discover-the-work-package-1-with-cea/
60	POLYPHEM article in European Energy Innovation magazine	Dissemination	29/09/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/09/29/polyphem-article-in-european-energy-innovation-magazine/
61	POLYPHEM final brochure	Communication	04/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/04/publication_polyphem_brochure/
62	Update - POLYPHEM at SolarPACES 2021	Events	05/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/05/update-polyphem-at-solarpaces-2021/
63	Conference proceedings : SolarPACES 2021	Scientific Publications	08/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/08/conference-proceedings-solarpaces-2021/
64	POLYPHEM 7th Project Meeting	All news	26/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/26/polyphem-7th-project-meeting/
65	POLYPHEM 1st Webinar on Small-scale Concentrated Solar Power (CSP): Challenges & Opportunities	Dissemination	15/11/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/11/15/webinar-small-scale-csp-challenges-opportunities/
66	POLYPHEM Newsletter – November 2021 Edition	Newsletter	18/11/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/11/18/polyphem-newsletter-november-2021-edition/
67	MEET THE TEAM: Discover work package 3 with CIEMAT-PSA	Dissemination	30/11/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/11/30/meet-the-team-discover-work-package-3-with-ciemat-psa/
68	POLYPHEM presentation in CINEA brochure	Dissemination	03/12/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/03/polyphem-presentation-in-cinea-brochure/
69	COVID-19: POLYPHEM is extended by 5 months	All news	07/12/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/07/covid-19_polyphem_extension/
70	POLYPHEM at ENLIT Europe 2021	Events	15/12/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/15/polyphem-at-enlit-europe-2021/
71	Watch the POLYPHEM 1st webinar!	Dissemination	13/01/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/01/13/watch-the-polyphem-webinar-on-small-scale-csp-challenges-opportunities/
72	Watch POLYPHEM's motion design video!	Communication	08/02/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/02/08/watch-polyphems-motion-design-video/

73	MEET THE TEAM: Discover the Work Packages 4, 7, and 8	Dissemination	09/03/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/03/09/meet-the-team-discover-the-work-packages-4-7-and-8/
74	Meet the team – KAEFER Corporate Competence Center Renewable Energies (CCCR)	Dissemination	05/04/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/04/05/meet-the-team-kaefer-corporate-competence-center-renewable-energies-cccr/
75	ENLIT 2021 & EU Projects Zone: Interview with Alain Ferriere	Dissemination	16/05/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/05/16/enlit-2021-eu-project-zone-podcast-interview-with-alain-ferriere/
76	Scientific publication: Thermal storage filler material distribution for the POLYPHEM project	Scientific Publications	25/05/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/05/25/scientific-publication-thermal-storage-filler-material-distribution-for-the-polyphem-project/
77	Save the date: POLYPHEM Final Infoday	Events	01/06/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/06/01/save-the-date-polyphem-final-infoday/
78	POLYPHEM Newsletter – June 2022 Edition	Newsletter	10/06/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/06/10/polyphem-newsletter10-june-2022-edition/
79	POLYPHEM Final Project meeting and Infoday	Communication	27/07/2022	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/07/27/polyphem-final-project-meeting-and-infoday/
80	The POLYPHEM project is now over!	Communication	31/08/2020	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/09/01/the-polyphem-project-is-now-over/

Annex 2 - POLYPHEM Dissemination & Communication activities

POLYPHEM – EU-H2020 Grant Agreement N°764048

Channel	Title	Place	Date (if relevant)	Links to the event or other online resources	Target Audiences							number of people reached	Dissemination level (local, regional, national, european, international)	Any IP conflicts ?	Responsible	
					Scientific Community	Industry	General Public	Policy-makers	Media	Investors	Customers					
1	Social media	LinkedIn POLYPHEM group	Online	01/04/2018	https://www.linkedin.com/company/polyphem/	x	x	x	x				210	International	NO	Euronovia
2	Social media	Joint CSP projects Twitter account	Online	01/04/2018	https://twitter.com/H2020CSP	x	x	x	x				400	International	NO	Euronovia
3	Website	Polyphem Website	Online	01/04/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/	x	x	x	x	x	x		1000	International	NO	Euronovia
4	Flyer/Brochure	POLYPHEM - Small-scale solar thermal combined cycle	online + prints	01/04/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/10/19/the-polyphem-brochure/	x	x	x	x	x	x		1000	International	NO	Euronovia
5	Participation to a Workshop	POLYPHEM - Small-scale solar thermal combined cycle	INEA 2nd internal CSP workshop, Brussels, Belgium	26/06/2018	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2018/07/10/polyphem-presentation-at-the-h2020-2nd-coordinators-workshop-on-csp/	x							27	Europe	NO	CNRS
6	Participation to a Conference	Centrales Solaires Flexibles de Petite Puissance: Le projet Européen POLYPHEM	JNES June 2018, LyonTech Campus in Villeurbanne, France	27/06/2018	https://ines-2018.sciencesconf.org/	x	x		x				Unknown	France	NO	CNRS-PROMES
7	Exhibition	Shared booth with two other H2020 CSP projects	8th ESOF Toulouse, France	09/07/2018	https://toulouse2018.esof.eu/en/	x	x		x	x	x		4000	International	NO	Euronovia
8	Participation to a Conference	The POLYPHEM Project: an Innovative Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle (poster)	SolarPACES 2018, Casablanca, Morocco	02/10/2018	https://aip.scitation.org/toc/apc/2126/1?expanded=2126	x	x		x		x		570	International	NO	CNRS-PROMES
9	Participation to a Conference	R&D on Thermal Storage in POLYPHEM (Poster)	SolarPACES 2018, Casablanca, Morocco	02/10/2018	https://aip.scitation.org/toc/apc/2126/1?expanded=2126	x	x		x		x		570	International	NO	CIEMAT-PSA
10	New sletter	H2020 joint CSP - New sletter #1	online	01/11/2018	Link	x	x		x	x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia
11	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	'Polyphem' – How two KAEPER engineers are planning to change the world!	KAEPER Magazine for Employees, Customers and Partners	05/02/2019	https://www.kaeper.com/Binaire/s/Binary1545/K-WERT-Nr_36-EN.pdf	x	x	x		x			200	International	NO	KAEPER
12	New sletter	H2020 joint CSP - New sletter #2	Co-hosting a workshop on: "New generation of Concentrated Solar Power Technologies" (IN-POWER, Nextower, RESLAG, POLYPHEM and CYSTEM	Online	01/04/2019	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/CAMP_AIGN_1712015_42.pdf	x	x		x	x		180	Europe	NO	CNRS-PROMES
13	Organisation of a Workshop	Shared a booth with two other H2020 CSP projects	Smart Energies Expo conference, Paris, France	17/06/2019	https://smart-energies-expo.com/2019/	x	x		x	x	x		3500	International	NO	Euronovia
14	Exhibition	Joint exhibition booth with other CSP projects	CSP Plaza Conference, Suzhou, China	10/07/2019	http://cpc2019.cspplaza.com/EN.html	x	x		x	x	x		800	International	NO	Euronovia
15	Exhibition	Roll-up poster in the EU Corner zone	5th edition of the ORC Power Systems Conference, Athens, Greece	09/09/2019	https://www.orc2019.com/uploads/File/ORC2019-Program.pdf	x	x		x				300	International	NO	Orcan Energy
16	Participation to a Conference	Prediction of Thermocline Zone Development at the Beginning of Dynamic Processes in Single Storage	SolarPACES, Daegu, South Korea	01/10/2019	https://www.solarpaces.org/	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	CIEMAT-PSA
17	Exhibition	Shared booth with other H2020 CSP projects	SolarPACES, Daegu, South Korea	01/10/2019	https://www.solarpaces.org/	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	Euronovia
18	Participation to a Conference	Design of an Experimental Prototype of a Solar-Driven CCGT Plant with Thermal Storage Based on an Existent Solar Power Tower Facility	SolarPACES, Daegu, South Korea	01/10/2019	https://www.solarpaces.org/	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	Fraunhofer-ISE
19	New sletter	H2020 joint CSP - New sletter #3	online	01/11/2019	Link	x	x		x	x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia
20	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	The Polyphem history by KAEPER	online	11/11/2019	http://www.cspfocus.cn/en/market/detail_2324.htm	x	x	x		x			150	International	NO	KAEPER
21	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	CSP Focus & the POLYPHEM history by KAEPER	online	11/11/2019	http://www.cspfocus.cn/en/market/detail_2324.htm	x	x		x	x	x		2000	International	NO	KAEPER
22	Participation to a Workshop	POLYPHEM - Small-scale solar thermal combined cycle	INEA 3rd internal CSP workshop 2019, Brussels, Belgium	26/11/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2020/01/07/polyphem-presentation-at-inea-3rd-h2020-coordinators-workshop-in-csp/	x							25	Europe	NO	CNRS
23	New sletter	H2020 joint CSP - New sletter #4	online	29/11/2019	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2019/12/04/h2020-csp-new-sletter-november-2019/	x	x		x				1500	International	NO	Euronovia
24	Other	ZENODO & POLYPHEM Community	online	31/03/2020	https://zenodo.org/communities/polyphem/	x	x		x					International	NO	Euronovia
25	New sletter	Joint Horizon 2020 CSP Project - New sletter #5	online	01/04/2020	Link	x	x		x	x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia
26	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Rural Digital Europe & POLYPHEM presentation	online	15/07/2020	https://rural-digital-europe.openair.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020:d643a2d1728f34726aa3d9c86ed31	x		x					500	Europe	NO	Euronovia
27	Exhibition	Virtual booth	SolarPACES 2020 Online	28/10/2020	https://www.solarpaces.org/	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	Euronovia
28	Participation to a Conference	Simulation-Based Comparison of Different Operating Strategies for a Dispatchable Solar-Driven CCGT Plant with Stratified Thermal Storage	SolarPACES 2020 Online	28/10/2020	https://www.solarpaces.org/	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	Fraunhofer-ISE
29	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Wikipedia & Thémis	online	26/11/2020	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_mis_(solar_power_plant)	x	x	x	x	x	x		181	International	NO	Euronovia

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31	New sletter	Joint Horizon 2020 CSP Project - New sletter #6	Online	01/01/2021	Link	x	x		x	x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia
32	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	POLYPHEM article in European Energy Innovation magazine	Online	29/09/2021	https://www.europeanenergyinnovation.eu/Portals/0/publications/EuropeanEnergyInnovation-Autum2021.pdf	x	x		x	x	x		1000	International	NO	Euronovia
33	Flyer/Brochure	POLYPHEM final brochure	Online + Prints	04/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/04/publication_polyphem_brochure/		x	x		x			1000	International	NO	Euronovia
34	Participation to a Conference	Virtual booth - SolarPACES 2021	Online	01/10/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/10/08/conference-proceedings-solarpaces-	x	x		x		x		500	International	NO	Euronovia
35	New sletter	POLYPHEM New sletter #7	Online	16/11/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/11/18/polyphem-new-sletter-november-2021-	x	x		x	x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia
36	Flyer/Brochure	POLYPHEM presentation in CINEA brochure	Online	29/11/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/03/polyphem-presentation-in-cinea-brochure/				x				1500	International	NO	Euronovia
37	Exhibition	POLYPHEM shared pod w ith other H2020/Horizon Europe projects w orking in the European Energy landscape	Online - ENLIT Europe Conference	30/11/2021 - 01/12/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2021/12/15/polyphem-at-enlit-europe-2021/	x	x	x	x	x	x		10 000	International	NO	Euronovia
38	Exhibition	POLYPHEM virtual stand in the EU projects zone	Online - ENLIT Europe Conference	30/11/2021 - 01/12/2022	https://www.enlit.world/projects/polyphem/	x	x	x	x	x	x		1500	International	NO	Euronovia
39	Organisation of a Workshop	POLYPHEM Webinar on Small-scale Concentrated Solar Power (CSP): Challenges & Opportunities	Online + replay	13/12/2021	https://www.polyphem-project.eu/2022/01/13/watch-the-polyphem-webinar-on-small-scale-csp-challenges-	x							300	International	NO	CNRS, CIEMAT, Fraunhofer
40	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	Cordis & Polyphem – Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle (Gas Turbine/ORC)	Online	07/04/2022	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/764048/fr	x	x		x	x	x		500	Europe	NO	Euronovia
41	Other	The EU Project Zone Podcast: POLYPHEM w ith Alain Ferriere	Online	04/05/2022	https://www.enlit.world/solar/the-eu-project-zone-podcast-polyphem-w-ith-alain-ferriere/	x	x	x	x	x	x		2 500	Europe	NO	Euronovia
42	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	Polyphem – Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle (Gas Turbine/ORC)	Online	01/06/2022	https://www.ise.fraunhofer.de/en/research-projects/polyphem.html	x	x	x		x			1000	Europe	NO	Fraunhofer
43	Social media	Visit of @Impvement-sudoe	online	25/07/2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6955503536709206016/?actorCompanyId=1	x		x	x				300	Europe	NO	Euronovia
44	Social media	Repost of the journal article "Font-Romeu, Résistance et avant-garde de l'énergie solaire" published by Charlie Hebdo in 29 July 2022	Online	01/08/2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6959115203271659520/?actorCompanyId=18696825		x	x		x			2 200	National	NO	Euronovia
45	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	KCORC & POLYPHEM	Online	Unknow n	https://www.kcorc.org/en/rd-projects/polyphem/	x	x		x		x		1500	International	NO	Euronovia
46	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	CIEMAT - ALMACENAMIENTO TÉRMICO Y COMBUSTIBLES SOLARES	Online	Unknow n	https://www.psa.es/es/areas/atvcos/proyectos/polyphem.php	x	x			x			500	Europe	NO	CIEMAT
47	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	UMI Community & POLYPHEM presentation	Online	Unknow n	https://community.umi.us/publication/5ea0029f2923d0869acc84c5	x	x	x			x	x	1000	International	NO	Euronovia
48	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	Aalborg CSP & POLYPHEM	Online	Unknow n	https://www.aalborgcsp.com/en/or-co-funded-projects/polyphem		x				x	x	1000	International	NO	Aalborg CSP
49	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	CNRS-PROMES & POLYPHEM	Online	Unknow n	https://www.promes.cnrs.fr/valorisation/projets-internationaux-et-europeens/	x	x			x			500	Europe	NO	CNRS
50	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	CEA & POLYPHEM	Online	Unknow n	https://liten.cea.fr/cea-tech/liten/Pages/Collaborer/Programmes-collaboratifs/Projets-europeens-en-cours.aspx	x	x			x			501	Europe	NO	CEA
51	Non-scientific and non-peer-review ed publication (popularised publication)	EURO & POLYPHEM	Online	Unknow n	https://euronovia.eu/nos-projets/	x	x			x			1500	International	NO	Euronovia